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Innovative pre-fabricated components including different **W**aste construction materials reducing building **E**nergy and minimising **E**nvironmental impacts

TRAINING MANUAL

COORDINATOR

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1. Introduction

This document presents structure and outcomes of the InnoWEE project (Horizon 2020 R&I Programme, Call EeB-04-2016, Grant Agreement no. 723916), and provides an overview of its main phases and achievements.

1.1. Consortium

InnoWEE is a research and innovation project funded by the European Commission and realised by ten partners representing research institutes, small and medium enterprises, industrial companies and municipalities from six of the European Union Member States (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. InnoWEE consortium partners

1.2. Project outline

In the European Union, the total waste approximately amounts to 2.5 billion tonnes (2016, EU-28), with the Construction sector contributing to more than one third of the total. Indeed, non-hazardous waste from construction and demolition (CDW) represents a huge stream (about 335 million tonnes in 2016) that has a significant potential for recycling, although a relevant part is still disposed in landfill or used for low added value destinations, e.g. road and foundation backfilling.

In addition, buildings account for about 40% of the total energy consumption in the European Union, and are deemed strategic in the frame of EU policies towards the improvement of Europe’s energy security, competitiveness and sustainability.

Within this framework, and according to circular economy approaches toward sustainability, the InnoWEE project aimed at developing prefabricated architectural panels for improved energy efficiency of buildings, made of innovative geopolymer binders embedding high quantities of aggregates recycled from CDW (Fig. 3). These panels were designed for low environmental impact, low embodied energy, low CO₂ emissions and high thermal performance. Target installations include also existing buildings, with a special attention to those belonging to the Cultural Heritage.

Geopolymers are inorganic binders generally considered greener than Portland cement based materials, owing to their lower carbon footprint and to the possibility of using various waste or

secondary raw materials (SRM) as reagents. Within InnoWEE, two geopolymer materials were developed, i.e. a fluid mortar embedding 50% by weight of recycled inorganic aggregates, which is the main constituent of the panels, and a geopolymer wood particleboard embedding either 40% or 50% by weight of recycled wood aggregates. Part of the research was devoted at assessing feasible methods for processing CDW to obtain suitable recycled aggregates.

Three types of prefabricated modular panels were developed (Figure 2), two for exterior envelope applications:

- External Thermal Insulation Composite System (ETICS)-like panels;
- ventilated façade cladding panels;

and one for interior heating and cooling systems:

- radiant heating/cooling ceiling panels (developed also in an additional version, modified for vertical wall application, which was tested in laboratory only).

Figure 2. InnoWEE panels with their installation at the pilot house in Padua (Italy): (a) ETICS-like, (b) ventilated façade and (c) radiant ceiling panels

A Technology Upscaling Pilot Plant (TUPP) was conceived, designed and installed to allow a production of about 400 items, including trials to adjust the scaled up production, panels for testing performance and durability, and elements to be installed in real demo buildings.

The produced panels were applied to four real demo buildings to assess the installation methods and their performances in terms of thermal efficiency and durability. Furthermore, they have been validated in four virtual demo buildings through numerical simulations.

Figure 3. InnoWEE at a glance

The InnoWEE project’s activities are implemented considering specific objectives.

To develop realistic performant and cost-efficient solutions with innovative products for new and existing buildings.

Recovery, disassembling and selection of CDW to yield suitable secondary raw materials and development of new high performance prefabricated versatile geopolymers panels.

To verify the performance of the panels installing them first in a pilot and then in 3 real demo sites. To model the real and “virtual” demo sites with different climate to obtain different scenarios.

Introduction and incisiveness of the new construction materials and solutions in the markets for new and existing buildings thereby creating new business and real estate development opportunities.

Development of information guidelines for applications installation and training on the new solutions and dissemination of the results.

1.3. InnoWEE stages

The InnoWEE project was planned according to specific stages as follows:

1. In the first phase of the project, the identification of eligible inorganic and wood CDW was carried out to develop and assess a satisfactory processing of the waste to obtain suitable recycled aggregates, thus transforming CDW into Secondary Raw Materials (SRM). This phase involved the upgrade of an existing plant for the treatment of CDW destined to road backfilling, which was modified to obtain recycled sands with particle size ≤ 2 mm.
2. Then, two geopolymer binders were developed, one with inorganic aggregates (High-Density Geopolymer – HDG) and one with wood aggregates (Wood Geopolymer – WG). The former was the main component of all the panels (possible insulation excluded), while the latter, in form of a thin layer, was applied to the backside of ventilated façade elements and was used in the modified version of wall radiant panels. The optimization of the binders involved the adjustment of technological features of fresh materials to comply with requirements of the pilot plant, and the extensive testing of mechanical/physical properties of hardened materials to deliver panel prototypes with satisfactory quality.
3. The prototyping phase, partially overlapped with the development of the binders and the pilot plant setup, was devoted to identify the main features of the panels in terms of sizes, shape, etc., and to preliminarily test their performances, as well as to provide the necessary indications for the design of the pilot plant. A preliminary installation test of external panels was carried out on an isolated reinforced concrete wall at the CNR facilities.
4. After obtaining positive results in the laboratory, the pilot production of InnoWEE panels was performed in Greece by AMS in a specially modified Technology Upscaling Pilot Plant (TUPP). Wood geopolymer panels (WGP) were produced at CNR facilities in Italy. This phase involved the assessment of production methods, according to industrial quality management approaches. About 400 items were manufactured, including those for installation in demo buildings, and those for performance and durability testing.
5. Panels were installed in 4 real demo site buildings, extensively monitored before and after the installation to assess the thermal performance in real conditions. Durability has also been under observation. Results from monitoring were used in simulations performed on virtual demo building to validate impact and effectiveness of the intervention.
6. Finally, a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) was carried out to evaluate environmental impact of all the proposed solutions. Activities were finally completed by a Life Cycle Cost Analysis (LCCA) and by the development of an industrial and a business plan to define the market potential.

2. Development of new materials and panels

This section presents the research carried out to: (i) identify and process Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) to obtain recycled aggregates suitable for geopolymer materials, which are the main component of InnoWEE panels; (ii) develop the geopolymer binders, suiting the pilot plant requirements and able to deliver panels with satisfactory quality; (iii) design and tune features of panels and casting/curing methods.

2.1. Waste processing and use

Construction and demolition waste (CDW)

The geopolymer material used to manufacture InnoWEE panels embedded 50% by dry weight of inorganic recycled aggregates derived from CDW. CDW typically comprises inert mineral materials (concrete, bricks, tiles and ceramics, etc.), while there might be smaller amounts of other components (e.g. wood, glass, plasterboard, bituminous mixtures and tar). CDW accounts for approximately one third of all the waste generated in the EU (Fig. 4), for about 0.8-1 billion tons per year.

Figure 4. Construction waste among all waste generated in the EU (Eurostat).

When working with waste materials and their recycling into new products, different legislative documents need to be considered. In the case of InnoWEE where we have been dealing with CDW and recycling it into building products, at the least the following documents shall be considered:

- legislation related to waste;
- legislation related to new (building) products (section 2.5).

EU Legislation relevant to waste and transformation of waste into SRM

A specific list of documents exists, defining current waste treatments and procedures to obtain secondary raw materials.

General legislation on waste

- Waste framework directive 2008/98/EC;
- European List of Waste (COM 2000/532/EC);
- Commission decision 2011/753/EU;

- Waste Shipment regulation 1013/2006/EC;
- Landfill Directive 1999/31/EC;
- Acceptance in Landfills Decision 2003/33/EC;
- Regulation on organic pollutants No. 850/2004.

General legislation on materials

- The Construction Product Regulation 305/2001;
- The REACH Regulation 1907/2006;
- CLP Regulation No. 1272/2008.

For example, the production of a residue is an inevitable consequence of primary operation. Although not the main commercial product of the process, residues may be of value in a number of other ways and, as shown in Figure 5, are used either immediately or, in the longer-term, after recovery. In the former case, residue should be regarded as by-products and never as waste; in the latter case, once recovered, residue should cease to be waste and becomes products at the place of recovery.

Performance of construction products, including products from recycled materials, is covered by CPR - The Construction Product Regulation (CPR (EU) No 305/2011).

Waste materials cease to be waste after processing into products, and when they fulfil the number of specific criteria. Technical requirements for the use of CDW for construction purposes are regulated under the CPR.

Figure 5. Life cycle of a product

Figure 6. Difference on used legislation depending on waste or product

Table 1. Classification of the waste used in InnoWEE according to the European List of Waste

Waste type according to the European List of Waste	Waste status	Waste code
Concrete	Non-hazardous	17-01-01
Bricks	Non-hazardous	17-01-02
Mixtures of concrete, bricks, tiles and ceramics	Non-hazardous	17-01-07
Wood - untreated	Non-hazardous	17-02-01
Glass - uncontaminated	Non-hazardous	17-02-02

Waste identification, source separation and collection

EU acknowledges that an “improved collection of goods for re-use and recycling requires selective demolition and appropriate on-site operations as well”. The Waste Management Protocol (2016) is

aimed at increasing “confidence in the Construction and Demolition (C&D) waste management process” and “trust in the quality of C&D recycled materials”.

There are four main steps to achieve the goal of a rational management of CDW to obtain valuable SRM:

1. Pre-demolition audits – All materials to be generated have to be identified and their quantities have to be estimated. It has to be understood, what has to be separated at source (e.g. hazardous waste), what can be used/recycled and how waste will be managed. The pre-demolition audit has to be carried out before any renovation or demolition project, and for any material to be reused or recycled, and for hazardous waste as well, to “identify the C&D waste generated, implement proper deconstruction, and to specify dismantling and demolition practices”.

2. Waste management plan – The plan must consider how the different steps of the demolition will be performed and by whom. It should present which materials will be collected selectively at source, how they will be transported, but also what will be recycled, re-used or finally treated and how each procedure should follow. It should also clarify how to address safety and security issues and limit environmental impacts.

3. Selective demolition – According to the mentioned EU CDW Management Protocol, the procedure should be as follows:

- a) hazardous waste separation;
- b) deconstruction (dismantling including separation of side streams and fixation materials);
- c) separation of fixation materials;
- d) structural or mechanical demolition.

Dismantling should involve a wide range of materials, e.g. glass, window frames, marble elements, valuable wood species, sanitary ware, heaters, metallic components, insulation foam, etc. This improves both the purification of waste streams and the potential for reuse. The waste streams (e.g. concrete, bricks, masonry, tiles, ceramics, etc.) should be kept separated.

Figure 7. Example of building for selective demolition

Figure 8. Images from building sites with ongoing selective demolitions

4. Processing and treatment – As underlined by the Protocol, “following the waste hierarchy offers wide-reaching benefits in terms of resource efficiency, sustainability and cost savings”. Preparation for re-use, when possible, is a preferable option because it requires little or no processing, thus environmental impacts associated with reprocessing do not arise. On the other hand, disposal in landfill should be generally the last solution to choose. Many options exist, in accordance with the waste hierarchy:

- a) preparation for re-use;

- b) recycling;
- c) material recovery;
- d) energy recovery;
- e) other recovery;
- f) disposal.

CDW processing to obtain InnoWEE SRM

When selected CDW are transported to the processing plant, a visual check is performed first, to remove unwanted residues (plastic, wood parts, etc.). The remaining waste materials are blended together, coarser parts are crushed and stored around the raised embankment (Fig. 9). Then, materials are fed into the screen. A first magnetic separator is located in correspondence of the screen to collect possible metal scraps. The coarser fraction feeds the jaw crusher and, after the size reduction, a second magnetic separation is carried out. The processed material is stored, awaiting for required verifications and, then, marketed.

Figure 9. The first step of the CDW processing – crushing and magnetic separation

From the process of crushing and screening three size fractions are obtained: larger than 60 mm, smaller than 30 mm and between 30–60 mm. The 30–60 mm fraction was selected for the production of InnoWEE SRM owing to its generally low content of soil, organic substances, etc. This fraction is fed into a second hammer mill that operates the required volume reduction (Fig. 10). Further refinements by an additional screen were necessary to meet the desired dimensional range (≤ 2 mm).

Figure 10. Aggregates smaller than 2 mm received from CDW processing

To comply with the environmental prescriptions provided by the permit released by the Italian local Authorities to allow the upgrade of the plant, the following improvements were carried out (Fig. 11):

- **sound-absorbent barrier**, close to the processing area;
- **new pavement** and **water treatment system** to ensure the compliance with the local Water Protection Plan;
- additional **dust reduction system**.

Figure 11. CDW processing plant

End of Waste criteria

To comply with the EoW criteria specifically set by Italian Local Authorities, the obtained secondary raw materials are analysed in lab to verify that they meet the prescribed physical and chemical requirements. Tests are performed according to the specific procedures described in standards, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Procedures used to analyse different properties of the aggregates

CDW	ANALYSIS	PROCEDURE
Aggregate (concrete, brick, glass)	Morphology, aggregate type and shape	Microscopy
	Elemental analysis	XRF
	Mineral phase identification	XRD
	Specific surface	Area
	Dissolution in alkaline media (geopolymer reactivity)	Si, Al concentration in alkaline solution by ICP MS
	Quantification of carbonate	EN 12620, EN 196-2
	Sieve analysis (fineness)	Sieves (optional laser granulometry for fine fraction)
	Water absorption	EN 12620, EN 1097-6
	Density and loose bulk density	EN 1097-3
	Compressive strength	EN 1097-11
	Heavy metals	Leaching test
	Chlorides	EN 1744-1, EN 1744-5
	Sulphates	EN 1744-1
	Different organic compounds (TOC, PCB, PAH)	

2.2. Development of InnoWEE geopolymers

Geopolymers are inorganic polymers obtained from the reaction of an aluminosilicate powder with an aqueous alkaline solution (Fig. 12). They belong to the broader class of chemically activated ceramics, extensively studied by Davidovits and other researcher.

R = ions (K⁺, Na⁺, ...)
n = degree of policondensation
w = bound water
z = 1,2,3...related to the network (< 3 for 3D network)

Figure 12. Chemical structure of the geopolymers

Their carbon footprint is generally considered remarkably lower than that of the Portland cement. The use of Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) in Alkali Activated Materials (AAM) and Geopolymer binders, as either inert aggregates or partially reactive materials, has been investigated in the last years with encouraging results. AAM/geopolymers showed a remarkable flexibility in using numerous types of different industrial wastes and by-products, and seem to offer a promising alternative recycling option for CDW as well. In addition, they present a generally excellent behaviour against high temperatures.

Ingredients of the InnoWEE geopolymer binder

The geopolymer material used to manufacture InnoWEE panels embedded either 50% by dry weight of inorganic recycled aggregates derived from Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW), or 40-to-50% of organic wood waste aggregates. The High-Density Geopolymer binder (HDG) developed in the framework of InnoWEE, which is the main constituent of panels, is based on typical reagents, i.e. metakaolin, ground granulated furnace slag, fly ash, potassium or sodium silicate, and, finally, inorganic aggregates derived from CDW. These ingredients, mixed together (e.g. with a planetary or a concrete mixer) in the right proportions, will produce a material that can set at ambient temperature and, once hardened, will be similar to a common mortar or concrete, according to the size of the aggregate (Fig. 13).

Metakaolin. Pozzolanic material derived from the calcination of Kaolinite (i.e. China clay), a soft clay mineral (Al₂Si₂O₅(OH)₄), used mainly as additive for concrete. The mineral is heated at 600-800°C, then ground.

Furnace slag. Ground granulated blast-furnace slags are a glassy by-product obtained during the production of metals from the ore and coke, generally rich in CaO, SiO₂ and Al₂O₃. They are rapidly quenched below 800°C to improve their reactivity and hydraulicity, to be used as additive in concretes.

Fly-ash. Coal combustion product captured in coal-fired power plants, used as a pozzolan additive or partial replacement of Portland cement in concretes. It is mainly composed by spherical particles between 0.5 and 300 μm, with various components (SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃...). Class F fly-ash has less than 7% of CaO.

Alkali silicate solutions. They are usually produced from quartz sand, alkali carbonates like soda ash (Na_2CO_3) or potash (K_2CO_3), alkali hydroxides (e.g. NaOH , KOH), water and fuels. They have many applications, from Constructions (e.g. in coatings for concrete and masonry) to several industrial uses.

Recycled aggregates (SRM). Inorganic waste coming from selective demolition of ordinary buildings, processed to obtain suitable recycled aggregates.

Figure 13. Ingredients of inorganic HDG mixtures

Aggregates have been considered as almost inert materials, i.e. assumed not to take part in the geopolymer reaction. The inorganic waste includes concrete, mortar and fired clay bricks, tiles and other non-hazardous remains obtained from selective demolitions of ordinary buildings.

Optimization of the binder

The features of the most promising trial formulations were tested in panel prototypes to point out possible issues not apparent from material specimens. The optimization of the binder was a complex task that involved, at the same time, the achievement of:

- technological properties of the fresh paste suitable for the available pilot plant (in terms of viscosity, setting time, etc.);
- mechanical performance of the hardened material (measured via compression, splitting and bending strength) adequate for the quality of the panels;
- physical properties (e.g. drying shrinkage), combined with the mechanical performance, suitable to prevent most defects of the panels, like shape distortions, cracking, etc.

The task was carried out in a heuristic manner, combining extensive experimental testing on material samples (Fig. 14) and real scale panel prototypes.

Figure 14. Test properties: mechanical strength

In order to find the most promising formulations and, subsequently, to tune them to obtain the most suitable recipe, many parameters were explored. This means that numerous variations were applied to the formulations. Compressive strength was one of the main indicators that provided the basis for decision, but several other properties were systematically measured as well, e.g. indirect tensile strength; drying shrinkage; material density and open porosity; viscosity and setting time, (the latter in advanced phases).

Figure 15. Examples of explored parameters for the HDG

As an example (Fig. 15), we can mention some of the explored parameters: type of waste materials, their quantity and their blends; curing temperatures, type and quantity of alkali activator; metakaolin/slag ratio; quantity of fly ash; particle size distributions of the recycled aggregates.

2.3. Development of panels

ETICS-like panels

InnoWEE ETICS-like panels (Figure 16) are 40 cm × 90 cm wide, and were conceived as a modular prefabricated solution for external insulation. Panels are relatively lightweight (6.5 kg/panel, i.e. about 18 kg/m²), and they consist of a 8 mm thick plate of High-Density Geopolymer (HDG) that covers an insulation layer made of Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) 20 + 50 mm thick. The HDG skin embeds 50% by weight of Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) aggregates from mixed inorganic waste (crushed concrete, fired clay bricks, etc.). Panels can be potentially produced with various surface textures, and their surface protected with either a transparent or a coloured paint.

Figure 16. ETICS-like panels final design and features

The manufacturing of the HDG part is carried out with a process that involves a direct casting on the insulation plate. For enhanced safety, the HDG embeds a glass fibre mesh.

Figure 17. Laboratory production of prototype ETICS-like panels

ETICS-like panels are glued to the wall surface by means of common adhesives, and fastened with commercially available thermal-break fasteners applied to the shifted lips of the bottom insulation layer. The compliance with Eurocodes requirements for wind and earthquake actions was assessed, together with the bond strength between the layers. The minimum bond strength measured according to ETAG-004 is 0.08 N/mm².

Figure 18. ETICS-like panel's fastening system

Ventilated façade cladding panels

InnoWEE ventilated façade panels (Figure 19) are 59.5 cm × 59.5 cm wide, suiting a modular installation every 60 cm. Panels are relatively lightweight (9 kg/panel, i.e. about 25 kg/m²), thanks to their design. They consist of a 8 mm thick plate of High-Density Geopolymer (HDG) with stiffening ribs, bonded to a rear reinforcing Wood-geopolymer panel (WGP) 7 mm thick.

Figure 19. Ventilated facade panels design and features

The HDG is the same of ETICS-like panels, while the WGP is made with 40% of untreated wood aggregates from construction waste (e.g. pallets, carpentry boards, etc.) bound by a geopolymer matrix. As for ETICS-like, various finishing textures can be applied, and the surface can be protected with either a transparent or a coloured paint.

The manufacturing of the HDG part is done through a casting process using a suitable mould to shape the stiffening ribs. For enhanced safety, the HDG embeds a glass fibre mesh and a Ultra-High Tensile Strength (UHTS) steel cord. In a second step, a wood-geopolymer panel (WGP) - fabricated separately - is glued to the rear side of the HDG panel to reinforce it against impact.

Figure 20. Production of the prototype cladding panels.

Panels can be fastened either on a sub-frame or directly on the wall using commercially available pin-type anchors. Anchors are applied on the panels by performing hole drilling on their 3 cm thick main lips, either during fabrication or on-site.

Figure 21. Fastening system

The panel was assessed by 3D Finite Element Modelling (FEM) to check the compliance with design actions (wind and earthquake induced loads), according to Eurocodes. In addition, the strength of the pin-type anchoring system was experimentally tested according to the main principle of the standard ASTM C135.

Figure 22. Evaluation of seismic and wind loads safety through FE analysis

Radiant ceiling panels

InnoWEE radiant ceiling panels are 59.5 cm × 59.5 cm wide to match common false ceiling modules. The HDG, which is the same of ETICS-like and ventilated façade panels. The weight is 7.6 kg without water (8.1 kg with water). Panels embed about 6.5 m of a 10 mm PEX-a piping, whose shape 5 cm spaced.

PEX-a pipe connections on backside

Figure 23. Radiant ceiling panels – features

Panels can be supported by common metallic profiles (Figure 24) used for false ceiling installations, provided that they are assessed for the actual weight of the panels.

Piping connections, which are on the rear side, can be realized with any system compatible with 10 mm PEX-a piping. The piping is totally embedded into the geopolymer, maximising the heat transfer and thus ensuring a good temperature profile and a remarkable thermal efficiency, thanks to the thermal conductivity of the geopolymer ($0.77 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$).

Figure 24. Mounting supports

The insulation consists of 50 mm thick EPS, monolithically bonded to the 6 mm thick HDG radiant layer.

The manufacturing was done by a simple geopolymer casting process that involves the use of a shaped EPS panel with the pre-mounted piping, serving as a “stamp” during casting. Different surface textures (if desired) can be easily obtained during casting.

Figure 25. Prototype panel manufacturing

The High-density geopolymer (HDG), with a thermal conductivity $\lambda = 0.77 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$, provides the finishing plate and surrounds the piping, maximizing the heat transfer surface. The best features, in terms of HDG thickness and pipe spacing, were supported also by numerical simulations.

Figure 26. Radiant ceiling panels – design

The design was assisted by 2-dimensional (2D) parametric Finite Element Modelling (FEM), which allowed optimizing thickness of the HDG, distance from the surface and spacing of the piping.

In addition, 3-dimensional (3D) FEM simulations assessed the behaviour, showing good agreement with the experimental tests.

Figure 27. Simulations used to provide the best design of the radiant ceiling panel

Wood Geopolymer Panels (WGP)

Wood-Geopolymer Panels (WGPs) are similar to cement bonded particleboards (CBPB). They are manufactured with wood chips, obtained from untreated waste wood (e.g. pallets, carpentry boards, etc.) held together by a geopolymer binder developed on purpose and pressed to obtain a flat panel. Differently from most CBPB, the process is carried out at ambient temperature. The advantage

Figure 28. WGP panel features

is that compared to CBPB, the use of geopolymer instead of Portland cement allows a more rapid setting, being rather insensitive to the lignin release. As the geopolymer binder is more tolerant to different wood species, it allows use of a wider spectrum of wood sources. Concerning fire reaction, WGP is a non-flammable Class B material.

Figure 29. WGP panel manufacturing process

2.4. Performance and durability testing in laboratory

An extensive testing was carried out to characterize materials and panels, with reference also to durability issues, to impact resistance (ETICS-like and ventilated façade panels, envisaged for external applications) and thermal performance.

The durability assessment included extensive testing of physical and mechanical properties of HDG and WG mixtures, as well as impact and bond tests carried out on panel samples, as follows:

- porosity;
- water absorption (capillarity test);
- water vapour permeability;
- freeze – thaw behaviour;
- freezing in presence of de-icing salts;
- resistance to carbonation;
- alkali reactivity of aggregates;
- determination of Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC);
- thermal shock tests;
- bond strength between HDG and EPS layers (ETICS-like panels);
- impact resistance of ETICS-like and ventilated façade panels;
- bending strength of WGP before and after freeze-thaw cycles;
- fire tests on WGP.

Figure 30. Examples of test equipment and specimens for material testing (Hg-porosimetry, change in length in ASR test, carbonation resistance)

Figure 31. Examples of testing of panel specimens (hydro-thermal cycling, frost resistance, bending strength)

Tests were firstly performed on laboratory prepared samples, and later on samples from pilot production. Most of the results on panels were comparable to the cement based panels. Water absorption was slightly higher, i.e. 1.02 kg/m^2 (for ETICS-like panel) than required in ETAG 004 (where it should be $\leq 1\%$), and where in the case of higher values of water absorption, freeze test is required. Testing of freeze thaw resistance was performed and confirmed that there were no damage after 30 cycles of freezing thawing.

In order to improve the impact resistance mesh was incorporated into the panels during the pilot production, what improved the products into group “Zone II” which means that the panels are suitable for zones liable to impact from thrown or kicked objects, but in public locations where the height of the ETICS-like will limit the size of the impact.

Figure 32. Sulphate resistance of samples from laboratory production (left), and from pilot production (right) (tested according to ASTM C1012/C1012M)

Figure 33. Alkali silica reactivity of samples from laboratory production (left), and from pilot production (right) (tested according to ASTM C 227-10)

Chemical resistance was assessed by means of several methods, like alkali silica reactivity (ASR), carbonation resistance and sulphate exposure tests. Results of all these tests showed that geopolymer panels were resistant to carbonation, and that exposure to chemical solutions of sulphate and alkalis did not cause an expansion of the materials beyond the limits set for cement base materials (Figure 32 and Figure 33).

Test results obtained on laboratory and pilot produced panels have shown good correlation what means that up-scaling process was properly designed and performed.

Thermal performance testing

Modular radiant elements were tested in a 130 m³ jacket-type room, that contains a testing room of 40 m³ designed according to EN 14240 standard. The thermal output testing is performed in steady-state conditions: the power delivered or absorbed by the radiant panel is balanced by the thermal dummies or by the active system. The time constant measurement is made with a transient method, imposing a step heating and measuring the thermal response on the surface of the panel.

For ETICS-like panels the thermal resistance is determined with the Taurus TLP 800 Hot-plate device according to the standard UNI EN ISO 8302 (estimated error 3%). Four samples were measured:

- two ETICS samples, 26A (AMS batch 6 2018/06/26) and 26B (CNR-ICMATE batch 2018/08/01),
- two EPS plates (nominal thickness 50 and 20 mm).

Table 3. Results of thermal tests of the ETICS-like panel samples

Sample	Thickness [mm]	Thermal resistance at 10°C [m ² K ⁻¹ W ⁻¹]	Thermal resistance at 30°C [m ² K ⁻¹ W ⁻¹]
26A	79.1	2.04	1.88
26B	78.4	2.05	1.89
Durosol #1	50.0	1.51	1.40
Durosol #2	19.6	0.61	0.56

In testing the thermal performance of the ETICS-like panels, the ISO standard 13786:2018 describes a calculation method for the thermal dynamic characteristics of walls. Currently, no standards are available for the laboratory measurement of this quantities. Therefore, we propose a method to test the InnoWEE panels.

The measured temperature profiles of the thermal sequence are centred, scaled and fitted with a sinusoidal model. The time shift is calculated as the time difference between the maximum value recorded on the front and on the back surface of the sample. The final result is the average of multiple selections of 2 periods across the experiment. Starting from the measured value, it is possible to extend the results to a 24 hour period.

Figure 34. InnoWEE method to test thermal performance of the ETICS-like panels

A new test, based on transient conditions, is proposed to verify the durability of the geopolymeric radiant panels. The stress test consists in supplying the panel under investigation with hot and cold water with a defined time cycle. The cycle is repeated multiple times, to resemble the use of the panel in real use conditions. The infrared thermography and the visual monitoring showed that the panel condition was the same before and after the repetition of hundreds cycles.

Figure 35. Stress test for the radiant panels

2.5. Certification of innovative products

Under EU regulations, CE marking is mandatory for products covered by the Construction Product Regulation (CPR), where a harmonised product standard exists. This can be an issue for new or innovative products not covered or fully covered by harmonised standards (hENs).

Manufacturers of innovative products such as InnoWEE panels, not covered by hENs, can obtain CE Marking via European Technical Assessment (ETA) and associated Assessment and Verification of Constancy of Performance (AVCP).

The Technical Assessment Body (TAB) issues the ETA on the basis of a European Assessment Document (EAD) adopted by the European Organisation for Technical Assessment (EOTA). Within this procedure requirements for products shall address seven basic requirements, given in CPR:

1. Mechanical resistance and stability,
2. Safety in case of fire,
3. Hygiene, health and the environment,
4. Safety and accessibility in use,
5. Protection against noise,
6. Energy economy and heat retention,
7. Sustainable use of natural resources.

ETA thus includes information on the intended use and performance of a product. AVCTP is a harmonised system defining how to assess products and control the constancy of the assessment results.

After the first ETA is issued the EAD is published and is further used as harmonized technical specification (similar as a harmonized standard); enabling fixing of CE marking.

Products can be put on the market also through national assessment procedure, which is under the jurisdiction of Member States, and it can differ among different states. In case of national technical assessment the national legislation should be followed, but CE marking is not possible.

3. Pilot plant and up-scaled production of new panels

For the manufacture of InnoWEE HDG panels a proper production line was needed. AMSolutions from Greece performed a detailed analysis of needs and requirements and the design of the pilot production line. 6 σ (six sigma) methodology was applied to provide the best design and efficient production process.

3.1. Pilot plant – Main characteristics

There might be confusion to people non familiar with the industry and its specific terminology about the meaning of a Pilot Plant. The most modern, simple and accurate definition of the term Pilot Plant can be summarized as following:

A pilot plant is a flexible pre-commercial production system that exploits lab scale results of a new technology, aiming to upscale the lab production and/or to produce small volumes of new technology-based products, mainly for the purpose of learning about the new technology.

By this simple explanation we can really identify Pilot Plant use and main objectives, which are multi-leveilling as the knowledge obtained is then used for design of full-scale production systems and commercial products, as well as for identification of further research objectives and support of investment decisions.

Though, it needs to be understood that a Pilot Plant is a complex and demanding development from its beginning to its end. The investor has to take in consideration all risks related to the production, depending on the nature of the product needs to be upscaled. Also, the financial (cost of the Pilot Plant) and, obviously, the environmental issues that might rise during its operation must eventually be treated. This investment becomes even more difficult as in many cases, complex production processes needs to be incorporated and adjusted to the Pilot Plant design and development. Therefore, in most cases the flexibility in the production lines, providing the capability to be modified according to the needs of every manufacturing and testing process, is a basic key factor that needs to be seriously considered.

Consequently, it becomes evident that a pilot plant is not easy to be constructed and is rather expensive and difficult to be maintained without the use of highly experienced and skilled personnel.

3.2. Upscaling strategy definition

Trying to upscale the HDG panels was not an easy task. It was clear from the beginning that modern methodologies and techniques needed to be adopted in order to reach the desired result.

Therefore, AMS exploiting the previous experience gained from the Pilot Plant operation in the last years, decided to implement for the HDG panels production the 6 σ methodology which was firstly developed and presented by Motorola back on 1980's, known as DMAIC which means: **Define, Measure, Analyse, Improve, Control**.

With very simple words DMAIC is “a case driven procedure used for improving and/or optimizing and/or up-scaling processes and finally produce ZERO defects products”

Define: the first step is the identification of all products and production requirements, which will setup the design requirements and framework. This step is extremely important as these requirements will guide the design team to these procedures and techniques to ensure the safely development of the final design either for the production line or the product and finally to all their implementation to the pilot plant.

Measure: Once the 1st step is completed and all required production lines and equipment are set up and tested, then a range of samples of the products will be produced in the pilot plant and will be tested for their properties. The aim of this phase is not only to test the products, but also the production line and equipment performance. Therefore, depending on the initial test results in this Trial & Error period is necessary to determine the best possible setup of the production lines at the highest product quality.

Analyze: Throughout the Trial & Error period all results are collected and analysed according the means of severity, repeatability, quality, and a database of statistical data is developed, aiming to identify the defaulting areas, of each aspect involved in the upscaling process.

Improve: The results of the Analyze phase and the nature of the errors, omissions, defaults, quality issues that could have arisen, etc., is the input for the design team and/or the management team either to redesign some parts or elements or processes in the production line or even the final product if necessary, and a new set of Trial & Error period starts following the same processes as in phases Measure and Analyze, and can be repeated as many times as necessary in order to obtain the desired product and/or process. Once everything is satisfactory, then the personnel is trained to the final processes to get familiar with them.

Control: In this phase the Quality Benchmarks for the final product quality are concluded, and Quality Assurance polices are implemented to the overall process in order to achieve constant repeatability of all processes which will finally reflect to the production of a product which will be at the same quality standards at every production batch by the manufacturer.

DMAIC is very dynamic and we could say that is a self-learning manufacturing process, because of the constant loops of the interactive actions among the steps of the process, which are aiming to improve mistakes, defaults, or omissions at every stage of the process.

Figure 36. DMAIC methodology

Figure 37. Summary of the DMAIC methodology

3.3. Upscaling strategy roadmap

Every upscaling process needs not only a schedule to be followed, but also the most important aspect that is identifying the weak and strong points of the product itself, as this will determine every step during the upscaling process.

In order to better understand the InnoWEE products, several discussions and meetings were held with the developers of the HDG paste, and they allowed identifying:

- the materials needed for the production of the HDG paste;
- a lab scale production methodology;
- the approximate processes' duration (in lab scale);
- some of the processes' specific requirements, e.g. the viscosity of the paste, the humidity of the raw materials etc.;
- some of the required equipment;
- the product's main characteristics e.g. shape, geometry, dimensions etc.

Though, there were still a lot of issues related to the Pilot Plant Production that needed to be clarified and concluded before its commencement. Some of the most important issues needed urgently to be identified and resolved were:

- the auxiliary processes and utilities (what other processes would be needed for the production of the HDG paste, e.g. compressed air, nitrogen supply, storage equipment etc.);
- the critical tasks (which were the tasks that were defining the production time and could not be modified);
- the production tasks "influencers" (which tasks were influencing other production tasks and how they were influencing them);
- relationships among processes (e.g. what would be the effect if one process would fail and how this would influence the other production processes);
- personnel involvement (how many personnel is needed to execute the production of HDG paste, which are the working stations and how you can improve personnel efficiency during production);
- Health and Safety issues;
- prerequisites for production (what is needed before the production starts, e.g. storage area for raw materials, ambient conditions in the production line, etc.);
- mostly important, it was necessary to identify any hidden issues that might already exist and could be critical for the Pilot Plant up-scaling process.

To successfully identify all the parameters of all these issues, and to implement solutions in a still unknown upscaling process, was proven to be an extremely difficult process, mainly because of the amount and nature of the unknown factors and parameters needed to be taken in consideration.

Therefore, it was decided to go back in 6 σ methodology and search solutions to its inventory of tools and adapt the 4D or Double Diamond tool and split the overall process in 6 stages:

1. Preliminary Design (where all issues related to the design are identified);
2. Detailed design (where all production and equipment is detailed designed);
3. Modifications in Pilot Plant (all modifications of the detailed design applied in the Pilot Plant);
4. Trial & Error Period (testing of the production line and production processes);

5. Corrective Actions (all the corrective actions that are applied to Production line and processes, as they have been identified by the Trial & Error Period);
6. Finally, the actual production of the HDG paste.

With the aid of 4D tool we developed a sequence of interactive actions among Production phases, where there is a constant loop of action-testing-remedial action-production-testing and so on.

Figure 38. Six phases of the production process

3.4. Preliminary Design

Basic Flow Sheet

The most important document for the overall design of the production line in a Pilot Plant is the Basic Flow Sheet. It gathers all details and results from the lab scale production and implements them in blocks or boxes indicating their relationships and the production flow, as will be described further down on this presentation.

Briefly The Basic Flow Sheet helps the designers to identify:

- required production and its duration;
- the equipment to be used;
- the utilities to be needed;
- any auxiliary processes which might be involved;
- the role of the personnel;
- production's prerequisites;
- design specific requirements;
- design "influencers";
- any possible health and safety issues;
- the Quality Assurance Policy;
- the production cut-off points (where and how production stops in case of failure or defective products);
- the remedies to be applied in case of any kind of failures.

Figure 39. Preliminary design structure

It has to be underlined that the Basic Flow Sheet is the A-Z manifest when there is an upscaling process involved.

No matter what would happen in the future, e.g. if an investor would decide to further upscale the HDG paste, the same process as per Basic Flow Sheet description will be followed.

Therefore, it is considered as a Generic Document and all HDG paste production would be heavily dependent on the processes described in it.

Basic Flow Sheet Analysis

As mentioned before, the Basic Flow Sheet follows a specific format of blocks, which are able to provide us information for every individual process.

In the Basic Flow sheet below (Figure 40) it can be easily identified:

- Starting on the top with the process duration estimation;
- On the big blocks at its bottom with the equipment; utilities and auxiliary processes used during production process;
- What are the requirements prior production starts;
- In which points of the production the production will stop in case of a mistake or failure;
- And the most important, which are the remedial actions need to be followed for every process.

Figure 40. Basic Flow Sheet

Table 4. Examples of failures during the production process and ways to solve them

Possible failure and/or risk	Remedial action
Mixture's weight is not as per recipe	Add or remove mixture from the mould
Mixture's surface is uneven	Use of the trowel to level it and/or increase vibration time
Air bubbles do not appear on the surface of the mixture when vibrating	Increase vibration speed until air bubbles will appear or increase vibration time
Defects on EPS (broken edges, unscratched side etc.)	Replace EPS
Mixture seems that does not have the appropriate viscosity	Perform viscosity test
Viscosity test is not proper	Dump off mixture
Low viscosity	Add water
High viscosity	Increase proportionally the raw materials quantities
Mixture is not homogeneous	Increase mixing duration to obtain fully homogenization (if not added in Step 3)
Mixture is getting hot during mixing	Decrease revs per minute on mixer blade and/or cool down mixer's external surface
Paint is uneven on the surface	Follow Quality Assurance Policy (QAP)
Paint is not well applied	
Paint is not appropriate shade	
Paint does not dry on designed time	

Going further into the Basic Flow Block, we can see the results of this analysis in the form of a summarized Table 5, for example:

- the equipment requirements and how these requirements are influencing their design;
- which risks are involved with the current process;
- what are the minimum requirements and considerations for the utilities in use for the specific process;
- what other facilities and services are needed for this process to operate smoothly;
- the minimum Health and Safety issues during the process;
- and how this process influencing other production processes and needs to be taken into account during detailed design phase.

Table 5. Production line requirements

Task	Considerations to taken into account
Choice of the appropriate storage container for solid raw materials storage (e.g. vessels, tanks, silos, bags, etc.)	Mass
	Weight
	Water absorption
	Resistance to corrosion
	Toxicity
	Granulometry - morphology
	Other specific chemical characteristics
	Dust generation
Ambient conditions	Agglomeration
	Temperature
	Humidity
Maintenance - cleaning	Air flow – ventilation
	Ease of access
Storage capacity	Ease of operations
	According batch – on demand
Handling	Hoists, cranes, forklifts, pallets etc.
Auxiliary utilities	Vacuum for cleaning
	Compressed air for cleaning
	Water supply for cleaning
	Drainage
Other processes involved	Quality Assurance (QAP)
	Testing samples
Personal Protective Equipment	According the Health & Safety Plan
<i>Design influencers</i>	<i>Storage area geometry - space</i>
	<i>Type of raw material</i>
	<i>Ambient conditions</i>

Production simulations and key processes relationships

From the outcome of the tables presented above, and through various simulations and modelling matrixes, we were able to:

1. identify the critical paths of the overall process and develop a PERT diagram indicating their relationships;
2. setup a working stations diagram were each employee knew exactly what needs to be done and how;
3. analyse the production processes relationships (how and to which extent each process effects the other).

Figure 41. Process time relationships

The outcome was to:

- establish production line conditions – limitations;
- adopt pilot plant conditions – limitations;
- identify failures and risks during production.

As a conclusion, the most important factors and parameters crucial for the upscaling of the HDG panels were identified and highlighted.

Due to the nature of the HDG paste the most crucial identified factor was the Net Production Time (NPT). In other words, the time that the HDG paste remains workable prior to harden. This time has been quantified in 120 min, though further improvement has been achieved at the later stages of the Project by CNR. The NPT in all lab scale tests was proved to be depended on the:

- formulation’s viscosity (the more viscous the paste, the lower the NPT);
- the indoor conditions at the time of production (a warmer ambient during production results in lower NPT).

Casting was by fact the most demanding process in both of time and resources. For example an ETICS-like panel needs at least 5 minutes to be cast and secured, while a ventilated façade panel needs at least 7 minutes.

Curing and post curing phases required a lot of time for their completion in comparison to other processes, e.g. an ETICS-like panel can be produced in overall 20 min (up to casting), while curing and post curing processes for the same panel require 108 hours (i.e. 6480 min) to be completed.

Figure 42. Key production processes relationships

This condition seriously affects the production mode of a Pilot Plant operation. In this case the Pilot Plant operation should be conceived in a batch mode (production of panels in batches) and not in a continuous mode (non-stop production). Additionally, as a side effect to the overall upscaling process, it seriously affects the production logistics. Large quantities of produced panels would require larger ovens or drying equipment and larger post curing storage capacity, therefore a balance among the processes needs to be achieved, and all these parameters to be carefully taken into consideration during production phase.

Production Line Up-scaling Design Principle

For the production of semi-liquid (in the form of paste) materials usually two different production methodologies are applied:

1. Tower or gravitational production, where all raw materials are placed in storage areas one on the top of the other and processed at the bottom of the storage areas to form the final paste. This method was successfully implemented by AMS in LEEMA Project, very similar to InnoWEE methodology but obviously not the same.

Figure 43. “Tower” or “gravitational” plant setup

Figure 44. LEEMA project’s production line

2. The modular design, where modules are placed in different locations or areas in the Pilot Plant forming a production line which each module performs separately the process that is programmed to do.

Our choice was the modular design for the production of InnoWEE HDG paste. The reasons derived from the detailed design outcomes.

Figure 45. „Modular” production line concept

First, there was a height restriction in AMS Pilot Plant. TUPP cannot accommodate at 7 m height required for the tower design (as in the Figure 43 above).

However, even if there was a sufficient height to accommodate a Tower based Pilot Plant, we would not have chosen it. Because what was needed, was a flexible production line where modifications of the equipment and/or processes needed to be adopted quickly and easily, which would be difficult in a Tower Pilot Plant. Additionally, because of the uncertainty of the production of HDG paste (not being it an industrially proven technology where we could gather data related to its behaviour and performance), it was obvious that these kind of modifications and adaptations will occur. Therefore, (and as has been proven later) a range of modifications were required to obtain the optimal performance of the production line which allowed us to operate it either on batch or continuous production modes.

Having the experience of LEEMA project and the Tower Pilot Plant operated in this project, we knew that the production line needed to be easily accessible to operate it but also to maintain it, and in fact this was not met in LEEMA project as it was extremely difficult to operate and maintain the Tower Pilot Plant.

Because on the modular design basis, the need to operate the production line, is mainly based in automations which should mandatorily be implemented on it due to the nature of processes involved, resulting to minimizing the human interaction production process, reflecting to better control and fewer defaults, or mistakes or omissions during production.

“Modular” Design Principle

When starting the InnoWEE Project and after the results of the Preliminary design, our initial idea was to build up a Pilot Plant with a modular design in a single batch mode of 350 kg per batch.

Indeed, the results of the detailed design indicated that:

- a pre-mixer was not necessary in 3rd module;
- the 2nd module was not necessary;
- mostly important, the cleaning process was not addressed properly. It is worth mentioning that cleaning is a very important process during HDG production, as a proper cleaning of mixers, pumps and pipe works is necessary to avoid blockages or damages to the equipment, due to the rapid solidification of the HDG paste.

Therefore, the new and final principle of the Pilot plant production line is the following:

- the “Modular” operation as per TUPP limitations, e.g. height restrictions, space geometry etc., has been adopted;
- the 2nd mixer has been modified and used as a secondary production line in case of a failure of the main mixer;
- the adopted methodology of production supposes to produce up to 700 kg of HDG paste per batch (\pm 60–80 panels);
- converting this batch capacity to one day of production (8 h shift) the capacity of the Pilot Plant is up to 2800 kg (\pm 240–320 panels);
- this setup allows operation in a continuous mode if necessary;
- the majority of the processes (almost 80% of them) are automatic or semi-automatic processes;
- in this manner the human intervention during production is minimized.

Nonetheless, it needs to be underlined that the upgraded operation of the pilot plant, e.g. 4 batches per day, was not feasible for the TUPP as it was creating other side-effects, mainly to the logistics part of the production, e.g. to curing and post curing processes due to the large amount of produced panels as explained previously.

Figure 46. HDG modular production

The pilot production includes the following steps: preparation of materials (EPS, potassium silicate), premixing (premixing of K-silicate with polypropylene fibres, feeding of solid raw materials to premixing buffer, transferring of solid raw materials to main mixer), mixing, casting, curing, post-curing, panel assembly, painting and cleaning. The detailed upscale production of all three types of the HDG panels is available in the following video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OTSx2FAvktc>

Figure 47. Premixing of solid raw materials to the premixing buffer

Figure 48. K-sil feeding to the main mixer

Figure 49. PP fibres to K-sil at the main mixer

Figure 50. Filling station

Figure 51. Casting

Figure 52. Curing chamber

TUPP's performance was above the expectations, as more than 400 HDG panels (ETICS-like, Ventilated and Radiant) were produced within a very strict schedule. HDG panels production proved to be straightforward and relatively easy, as far as the specific production conditions and limitations related to the material properties (mainly the working time and curing time of the HDG) are respected and followed.

Figure 53. ETICS-like panels upscale production

3.5. Detailed Design

Technology Upscaling Pilot Plant (TUPP)

AMS Pilot Plant is located 22 km at the North from Athens centre in Acharnes area, and covers an area of 552 m².

Figure 54. TUPP modules layout

The Pilot plant is equipped with:

1. All required infrastructure (electrical, BIM, water and deionised water supply, septic drainage, firefighting equipment, advanced ventilation system, gases distribution and failures detection network, compressed air, etc.)
2. Auxiliary systems (power backup systems such as UPS and generators, dedicated servers for BIM control, monitoring and controlling systems, etc.)
3. Fully equipped laboratory for a wide range of testing
4. A wide range of machinery and equipment e.g. mixers, conveyors, tanks, augers, motors, painting room etc.

TUPP was divided in 6 different modules were the 1st module accommodates the storage of solid raw materials and all processes involving them as premixing and feeding to main mixer. The 2nd module is dedicated to the storage of liquid raw materials and processes depending on liquid materials, such as feeding to main mixer and cleaning. The heart of the Pilot Plant is in the 3rd module where the main mixing and transportation of the HDG paste to the filling station is processed. The 4th module is solely dedicated to casting as is the most demanding in labour and resources activity during production. A curing oven and large storage area for post curing of the produced panels are located in the 5th module, while all other activities not related to the production of HDG paste, such as preparation of EPS, wood, assembly, painting packaging, are performed in module no. 6.

To understand the depth of the design of each module, in this screenshot of the 1st module, you can see some of the services involved as were identified and adjusted to each module requirements.

Production line simulations and modelling

When operating a Pilot Plant in a modular mode, is necessary to be sure even from the design phase that the production line would be performing as expected, and at the same time it does not conflict with other processes or regulations that might apply, and, mostly important, that it is safe during its operations for the personnel and the environment.

Therefore, a series of simulations and modelling with the aid of a sophisticated software (Pipe flow) have been executed in all crucial processes of the production. Briefly mentioned:

1. To the feeding line of the liquid raw materials (pipework and pumps);
2. To the hot and cold water used to produce the HDG paste (pipework, pumps and heaters);
3. To the mixing process (behaviour of pipework, mixer blades and pumps);
4. To the nitrogen supply that is used for the storage of the solid raw materials (to obtain a modified atmosphere within the silos to avoid any kind of contaminations, humidity, etc.);
5. The overall pumps performance when operating simultaneously;
6. Finally, probably the most important simulation was the cleaning process of the overall production line, which identified the parameters and constrains needed to adopted in order to maintain the production line at workable condition at all times.

Production line design and equipment modifications

During the production line design, the production line in TUPP and its equipment have been modified and adapted to the requirements of HDG paste production. For example:

- the main mixer was modified (twice);
- the premixing buffer was added;
- the feeding augers adjusted to the right height;
- scales were redesigned and calibrated;
- PLCs were reprogrammed (three times to adjust optimal processes);

- a new scale for the main mixer was developed;
- a more sophisticated load cells design with accuracy of 10 g was developed;

In total, more than 200 modifications were executed to the existing line prior and during Trial and Error Period. Implementation of the modifications in the TUPP started in May 2017 and was completed in May 2018, when AMS started the production of InnoWEE HDG panels.

Figure 55. Production line design and equipment modifications timeline

3.6. Analyse & Improve – Production data

Production – statistical data

One of the key points in 6σ methodology, as mentioned above, is the data collection. These data collected throughout all production processes (Fig. 56) are indicating:

- 57.57% (19 failures) – human involvement (instructions implementation 11, corresponding at 33.33% and lack off maintenance 8, corresponding at 24.24%),
- 12.12% (4 failures) – design errors,
- 15.15% (5 failures) – manufacturer’s hardware failures, and
- 9.09% (3 failures) on unpredictable or other causes such as local power failures in Acharnes area,
- 6.06% (2 failures) the cause could not be identified and is related to component failure.

Figure 56. Mechanical or equipment failures distribution

Analysing further these data, it was observed that there is a constant improvement among the production phases starting from the Trial & Error phase to the high risk production phase. Almost the 84.8% of the failures occurred during the setup period of the pilot plant (Trial & Error phase, Initial batches and intermediate batches) while only 6.06% of them occurred during normal production of the HGD panels.

Figure 57. Failures by cause timeline

Additionally, analysing the severity of failures occurred, we notice that the 64,5% of these failures were of low importance and only 7.75% were high risk failures (which is worth to be mentioned that occurred during the general power blackout sessions due of the weather conditions in all of the city during production phase).

But the most important aspect of the statistics are probably the total production statistics:

- 416 panels (including lab testing) were produced,
- over 3000 kg of geopolymmer paste were processed,
- actual production duration was 53 days (while 27 of them at night shifts due to the extreme weather conditions – heat in Greece during summer).

While the overall performance based on the 6σ methodology is proven by the defective panels produced which were:

- in ETICS-like panels production: 2.1%,
- in ventilated façade panels: 0.63%;
- in radiant panels: 0.33%.

Figure 58. Defective products by cause

Analysing the causes of defects that occurred, they were usual in every production of building materials, such as defects by impact, during transportation, shrinkage etc., but what it is worth to mentioned that almost half of the defects (49%) occurred by human intervention necessary for the production process.

Though, by looking at the figures of the defects occurrence analysis is clear that most of the defects (67.64%) occurred at the stages of setting up the production process, where the production procedures were not finalized and personnel was not familiar with HDG paste production, while on later stages of production defects dropped dramatically, showing a constant improvement.

Figure 59. Defective panels percentage per production stage

6σ ranking

As already mentioned, the 6σ methodology is targeting the manufacture of zero defects products. In most cases, especially for a pilot plant production, this is not feasible and it applies to high-tech productions such as aeronautics, electronics etc., where human involvement is limited. In our case, the actual scope of using the 6σ methodology is to constantly self-improve the production processes involved and to maintain the quality of the products produced at the same level.

Sigma level	Sigma shift	Defective Parts Per Million	Percent defective	Percentage yield
1 Initial Start	-0.5	691,462	69%	31%
2	0.5	308,538	31%	69%
3	1.5	66,807	6.7%	93.3%
4 End of ETICS Production	2.5	6,210	0.62%	99.38%
5	3.5	233	0.023%	99.977%
6 6σ TARGET	4.5	3.4	0.00034%	99.99966%
7	5.5	0.019	0.0000019%	99.9999981%

Figure 60. TUPP’s Performance ranking in 6σ methodology for ETICS-like panels production

When HDG panels production started, during Trial & Error period the pilot plant effectiveness was between level 1 and 2, in ETICS-like panels production the effectiveness rose between level 3 and 4 and was maintained in the same rank during all types of panels production.

But from the figures it is clear that in every stage defective products were reduced, thus indicating a constant improvement for the production process.

Finally, the overall 6σ ranking was 3.06% between levels 3 and 4, while the usual ranking for a pilot plant production is between levels 2 and 3, proving that HDG panels production in TUPP was above the industrial standards and the TUPP operation was successfully above the expected performance.

Figure 61. Analysis of the production phase in 6σ ranking

4. Installation, monitoring system and performance appraisal in real demo buildings

After the up-scaled production performed in Greece by AMSolutions, panels were transported and installed in 4 demo buildings located in Padua (Italy), Athens (Greece), Bucharest (Romania) and Putte-Mechelen (Belgium). They were extensively monitored before and after the installation to assess the thermal performance in real conditions, and durability has been under observation as well. Results from monitoring were also used in simulations performed on virtual demo buildings to validate impact and effectiveness of the intervention. Installations were as follows:

- Pilot House in Padua (Italy) – ETICS-like, ventilated façade and radiant ceiling panels;
- Old city hall of Voula, near Athens (Greece) – ETICS-like and ventilated façade panels;
- Don Orione residential care centre in Bucharest (Romania) – ETICS-like panels;
- Residential Eco-house in Putte-Mechelen (Belgium) – radiant ceiling panels.

4.1. Pilot house, CNR area of Padua, Italy

In the Pilot house three types of panel solutions were installed: ETICS-like panels, ventilated façade cladding panels and radiant panels (Fig. 62). Due to the specific features of the prefabricated structure, whose walls consist in sandwich panels with a metallic exterior, installation methods were adapted and may differ from the other demo sites.

Figure 62. Location of each type of panels in the plan view of the Pilot house in Padua, whose south and east façades are shown on the right

Installation of ETICS-like panels

In the North façade, 28 ETICS-like panels were installed (Fig. 63) according to the following procedure:

- alignment of the base panels through a bottom metal profile;
- application of a suitable adhesive on the metal sheet structure;
- positioning of the panels and application of thermal break fasteners passing through the wall and bolted on the interior side;

Figure 63. ETICS-like panels installed on the Pilot house's north wall

- filling of the joints between panels with a suitable elastic adhesive;
- installation of a metal flashing to protect top and lateral edges of the installation.

Installation of ventilated façade panels

30 ventilated façade panels were installed on the South façade (Fig. 64), by means of a dedicated steel frame anchored to the soil and fastened to the building only at the top to limit the perforation of the wall, as follows:

- fastening of the 4 columns of the steel frame with bolts;
- drilling of the panels in 4 points (2 holes in the upper side, 2 in the lower one);
- fixing of the fasteners to the horizontal profiles of the frame;
- installation of the panels by means of the anchors pins;
- installation of a metal flashing to protect top and lateral edges of the installation.

Figure 64. Ventilating façade cladding panels installed on the Pilot house south wall

Installation of radiant panels

30 radiant panels have been installed in an interior room, leaning on 7 steel omega profiles that supported a plasterboard false ceiling (Fig. 65). In order to have the correct temperature and to provide the flowrate necessary to the radiant panel system, the water supply system has been modified. Two new pipelines have been added, one for the radiant panel and one for the dehumidifier. The panels have been connected in Tichelmann system (reverse/return) in order to have the same pressure losses in the supply and return. Five series of 6 panels have been connected in parallel.

Figure 65. Previously installed false ceiling (left), replaced by InnoWEE radiant panels (right)

Performance and durability monitoring

The monitoring system is composed by:

- one thermo-flux meter installed in the north wall of the building to calculate the thermal transmittance of the wall before and after the installation of the ETICS-like panels;

- six thermal energy metering (flux meter, inlet and outlet water temperature meter), one for every fan coil installed to know the energy consumption of every rooms, one for the radiant panels and one for the dehumidifier;
- four different microclimatic sensors in the rooms to know their internal thermal condition;
- special instruments for *ad hoc* campaign for the evaluation of the thermal performance of the wall and ceiling;
- an outside weather station to monitor the outside temperature and the climatic condition;
- a globe thermometer campaign pursued during the winter and summer season before and after the installation in order to calculate the thermo-hygrometric indoor condition (PMV and PPD).

Figure 66. Radiant panels monitored during work in cooling mode

Figure 67. Location of the monitoring equipment for ETICS-like and radiant panels in the building plan

The installed local monitoring of the ventilated façade panels is composed by contact temperature, air cavity temperature, air velocity and humidity sensors. The infrared monitoring shows also the performance of the installed radiant panels compared to the previously installed ceiling. The surface temperature distribution is comparable to the laboratory testing done before the installation in the pilot site.

Figure 68. Monitoring equipment installed to monitor performance of the ventilated facade panels

Durability and resistance to wear of exterior solutions was also investigated. The following test methods were selected to be used on-site based on preliminary in-lab investigations: surface water

absorption (SWA), surface hardness (SHT), ultrasonic pulse transit time (UPV) and Eigen (resonant) frequency based test (EFT).

On Padua test site the ventilated façade located on the south side of the building and the ETICS-like façade located on the north side of the building were monitored. Three series of measurements have been accomplished so far: in spring 2019, in autumn 2019 and end of summer 2020, to reach whole year of exposure.

In Figure 69 respectively the ultrasonic pulse velocity test results of the ventilated and ETICS type façade are presented as an example.

Figure 69. Ultrasonic pulse velocity test results of the ventilated (left) and ETICS (right) type façade

All NDT test result of all three series of test are comparable which leads to the conclusion that no deterioration occurred during the summer 2019. Both, the ventilated and the ETICS façades are performing well.

4.2. Old city hall of Voula in Athens, Greece

Two exterior solutions have been installed in the Greek demo building, i.e. ETICS-like and ventilated façade cladding panels (Figure 70).

Figure 70. Location of each type of panels in the demo site

Installation of ETICS-like panels

For the installation of the ETICS-like panels the wall was prepared by removing any cables, pipework and other installations, and loose paint and plaster were removed as well. An L-shaped steel beam was fastened to the wall to provide a bottom support. Starting from the east side, ETICS-like panels were prepared for the installation. A thick layer of low expansion polyurethane (PU) foam was applied in a zig-zag pattern to the back side, then the panel was placed in position and fixed to the wall with thermal break fasteners. For the further rows the same installation technique as for the installation of the 1st row of panels was used, excluding the steps related to the beam attachment.

An elastic tile joint sealant was used to seal the joints of each panel. An aluminium profile with L-shape lip of 3 cm was used in order to cover the windows' lips and jumps. Low expansion PU foam was applied on the back side of it and secured with screws and fasteners. Finally, its edges were sealed with elastic joint sealant and painted with AMS multifunctional coating. Figure 71 shows the wall before and after the installation.

Figure 71. ETICS-like panels installed in Greek demo site

Installation of ventilated façade panels

To install the ventilated façade cladding panels, the wall was drilled as far as possible in a straight angle with a M22 in diameter drill attached on a drill hammer up to the depth of 150 mm. A bi-component chemical resin was injected into the anchor's hole with the aid of a mechanical gun. After that the anchors of the 1st panel (both the 4 of them) were inserted into the holes. The same process was repeated for all other panels in all rows but always allowing enough time to partial solidification of the resin in order to ensure accurate levelling of the pins. Excessive resin was cut off with the aid of a cutter.

Similarly, an aluminium profile with L-shape lip of 3 cm was used in order to cover the windows' lips and jumps. Low expansion PU foam was applied on the back side of it and secured with screws and fasteners. Finally, its edges were sealed with elastic joint sealant and painted with AMS multifunctional coating. Figure 72 shows the wall before and after the installation.

Figure 72. Ventilated façade cladding panels installed in Greek demo site

Performance and durability monitoring

The monitoring system is composed by:

- two thermo-flux meter installed in the two rooms in the north wall of the building to calculate the thermal transmittance of the wall before and after the installation of the new technologies. The temperature sensors installed in the wall will be useful to know also the internal and external surface temperature of the external walls;
- two different microclimatic sensors in the rooms to know their internal thermal condition;

- a weather station installed in the roof of the building;
- a globe thermometer campaign pursued during the winter and summer season in order to calculate the thermo-hygrometric indoor condition (PMV and PPD).

The monitoring of the ventilated façade installed is similar to those in the pilot site and it is composed by contact temperature, air cavity temperature, air velocity and humidity.

Concerning durability and resistance to wear of exterior solutions, the main objective of the Athens test site is similar to those of the Padua demo site, i.e. to test the durability of ETICS-like and ventilated facades, but in hot Mediterranean climate conditions.

The same test methods were applied: surface water absorption (SWA), surface hardness (SHT), ultrasonic pulse transit time (UPV) and Eigen (resonant) frequency based test (EFT). On Athens test site, the ventilated facade and the ETICS-like facade are located on the same side of the building. Two series of measurements have been accomplished so far: in spring 2019 and in autumn 2019. Further assessment foreseen to reach a whole year exposure was not possible due to Corona virus traveling restrictions.

In Figure 73 as an example hardness tests results of the ETICS-like and ventilated façades are presented.

All NDT test result of test set 2 are comparable to test results of test set 1 which leads to the conclusion that no deterioration occurred during the summer 2019. Both, the ventilated and the ETICS-like façades are performing well.

Figure 73. Surface hardness test results of the ventilated (left) and ETICs (right) type façade

Figure 74. Monitoring equipment for testing the ventilated facade (left), ETICS-like façade (top right) and indoor climate conditions (bottom right)

4.3. Don Orione residential care center in Bucharest, Romania

Installation of ETICS-like panels

In the Romanian demo site, ETICS-like panels were installed on two façades of the single-storey building, i.e. the North-East and the North-West walls (Fig. 75).

The installation of 77 ETICS-like panels was done starting by fastening an L shaped profile to the wall, serving as bottom support. The installation started with the bottom right panel. Each panel was installed using mortar and thermal break fasteners. Prior to installing the 5th line of panels, an L shaped 50x90 mm profile was applied to the wall along the perimeter of the window. To ensure protection from water infiltrations, on the top side of the façade an aluminium flashing was fastened. The joints between the panels were sealed with a suitable adhesive.

Figure 75. ETICS-like panels installed in the demo site in Bucharest

Performance and durability monitoring

The monitoring campaign is composed by:

- one thermo-flux meter installed in the room in the north wall of the building to calculate the thermal transmittance of the wall before and after the installation of the ETICS-like panels;
- two different microclimatic sensors in the rooms one inside the room to know their internal thermal condition and one close to the external wall;
- temperature and UR sensors installed outside to monitor outside conditions;

- electrical energy meter to monitored the energy consumption of heating and cooling system;
- a globe thermometer campaign pursued during the winter and summer season in order to calculate the thermo-hygrometric indoor condition (PMV and PPD).

With reference to durability and resistance to wear, the Bucharest demo site is the third demo site with the same objectives as the two previously presented ones. i.e. to test the durability of the ETICS-like panels in continental conditions with cold winter and hot summer climate. The same test methods were used as in case of the Padua and Athens demo site. Two series of measurements have been accomplished so far: in spring 2019 and in autumn 2019. Between the first and the second assessment the facade was repainted. Further assessment foreseen to reach a whole year exposure was not possible due to Corona virus traveling restrictions.

As the repainting should not have much influence on the ultra sound velocity test results, those are as an example presented in Figure 76.

Figure 76. Ultrasonic pulse velocity test results of the north (left) and west (right) facade

As the facade has been repainted between the first and the second assessment the evaluation of the test results is debatable, even so no major damages have been recorded so far – the ETICS-like façades is performing well.

Figure 77. Monitoring equipment for testing the ETICS-like façades

4.4. Eco-house in Putte, Belgium

Panels installation

In this residential eco-house, the InnoWEE radiant ceiling panels were installed along with a commercial competitor (Fig. 78), with the purpose of obtaining a direct comparison in heating and in cooling mode.

Figure 78. Eco-house and room where panels were installed

The selected commercial solution required two panels with dimensions 1.2 m × 2.0 m. To install the InnoWEE solution (15 items, grouped by 5 in 3 rows), an independent support structure was built not to affect the timber structure of the building. The prefabricated parts were fixed into place using anchors. All 8 metal pillars were fixed into place using metric screws. The beams were positioned and welded on the entire perimeter. After the metal structure was completed, the panels have been installed. In order to have enough space to connect each panel to the water circuits, a 600 mm gap between the panels and the ceiling was maintained. After positioning each panel, the water connection was made.

Figure 79. Commercial (left) and InnoWEE radiant panels (right) installed in the ceiling

Performance monitoring

The monitoring system is composed by a microclimatic sensor (temperature and humidity), a thermal energy meter (flow meter, inlet and outlet flow temperature) for the radiant system and a weather station in the garden outside the building. Globe thermometer campaigns were pursued during the winter and summer season in order to calculate the thermo-hygrometric indoor condition (PMV and PPD).

Figure 80. Monitoring equipment to measure performance of the radiant ceiling panels

5. Building Energy Modelling (BEM) and virtual demo sites

The main goal to be achieved in the task related to Building Energy Modelling in the InnoWEE project was the identification of the best solutions for an easy installation and disassembly of panels based on architectural evaluation and costs. For this purpose a proper collection of data and setting of final requirements of the real demo sites have to be performed. The data are used for optimizing the solutions by modelling their energy performance for the elaboration of the project design for each demo building.

Figure 81. Correlations between WP4 and other WPs of the InnoWEE project

5.1. Evaluation of the installation/dismounting technologies and methodologies and panels monitoring

Three types of InnoWEE geopolymeric panels have been installed in 4 demo buildings. Each installation was analysed and evaluated, based on time and cost needed to perform the process.

ETIC FAÇADE	VENTILATED FAÇADE	RADIANT PANELS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Panel to be glued on the vertical wall with mortar Mechanical fixing with thermal break fasteners Silicon sealing to cover joints between panels Metal flashing installation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wall anchoring system Panels on-site drilling Levelling and mechanical fixing of panels Metal flashing installation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To be mounted in common systems for false ceilings Test installation not carried out Conventional fasteners and anchoring systems suitable

Figure 82. Summary of InnoWEE panels' installation methodology

The evaluation of the installation is presented below, where the costs are referred only to the installation operations. Other factors affecting the final price of the products are: place of installation, architecture of the building, conservation status.

For an effective evaluation of costs all factors that affect the final price of the products have to be considered:

- Place of installation: Each of the countries where the panels have been installed has different histories, traditions, paths towards development, political and economic aspects. Due to

that reason, it is not possible to have aligned costs for each place because they vary according to the evolution of each one.

- Labour: It has different costs depending on the country. In Belgium labour cost are high, in Italy are moderate, and while in Greece and Romania are very low.
- Geometry: The geometry of the buildings varies case by case. Some buildings have simple geometries, other are more complex, some have overhangs or recesses and others have corners.
- Windows: Some buildings have windows on the facades, so it occurs a major attention to cut and fix the panels.

ETICS-like panels

The ETIC-like panels have been installed in two real sites, after the installation test on a free standing reinforced concrete wall. The advantages of the ETICS-like panels depend on several factors and they change in relation to the type of the building and the place where the building is set.

For the ETICS-like panels the advantages are related to the fact that there is only one installation phase, and the installation itself is simpler than a traditional ETICS system. The number of fixing is reduced, and the aesthetical result is better than a traditional one.

From the installation carried out the structure of the buildings had a fundamental role in term of time and costs. In Padua, where the structure of the building was a lighten structure made of sandwich panels, it was necessary to have lots of fixings and passing bars to ensure the secure fixing of the panels. Furthermore, due to this reason, an adhesive compound was needed to be spread in the holes done for the passing bar, to ensure the insulation.

In Bucharest and in Voula the installation was easier than in Padua, because the structures of the buildings were a traditional walls made of airbricks or concrete. The difficulties were related to the geometry of the buildings – presence of windows and corners.

The average installation time per panel, considering a middle trend of the installation time for Padua and Bucharest, could be considered of 5÷10 minutes per panel, that means about 10÷25 min/m². The time taken for a traditional ETICS solution can be considered about 40 min/m².

Regarding the installation costs, the InnoWEE solution costs about 20-30 €/m² depending on several factors. A traditional price can be considered about 30 €/m².

Taking into consideration also specific installation factors, such as: scaffolding, Health & Safety costs and even design, the costs of the InnoWEE solution are foreseen to be between 54.00-97.36 €/m².

The main pros of InnoWEE solution in term of times if compared to a traditional solution are the followings:

- Precast panels;
- Only few steps are needed to install panels;
- Easy installation method;
- The panels weigh little and are easily handled as they are small.

Ventilated panels

Ventilated panels have been installed in Padua and in Voula, after the installation test on a free standing reinforced concrete wall in Padua. The advantages of the ventilated panels depend on

several factors and they change in relation to the type of the building and the place where the building is set.

In the building of Padua, the installation of the panels took more time than in other sites because of the existing structure of the building. In fact, the structure of the Pilot House is made of light walls of sandwich panels, so it was needed to design and mount a secondary structure on which hang panels. Furthermore, all the panels had to be cut on site by hand.

The critical issue was the design and mounting of a secondary structure, necessary for structural reasons, that entailed more time and higher costs.

The other phase that required more time was the phase of the drilling panels by hand – this operation required a high level of accuracy.

Anyway, the main pros of InnoWEE solution, if compared to a traditional one, is having precast panels with a little weigh and easily handled due to the small dimensions.

From the installations carried out at the different demonstration sites it was possible to estimate the time taken and the costs incurred, so that they could be compared with the times and costs of similar solutions present on the market.

Of course, it is necessary to consider that the comparison is done taking into account that the buildings had different characteristics, so even different steps were needed to complete the installation. Even cost, as already said, varies because of several reasons: typology of building, installation methods, labour cost.

From the required results it can be defined an average installation time per panel of 5÷15 minutes, which means about 10÷30 min/m². The time taken for a traditional ventilated façade can be considered about 20 min/m².

Regarding the installation cost, the ventilated InnoWEE solution costs about 20-40 €/m² excluding the anchors system which varies a lot depending of the building structure. A traditional price of a ventilated façade can be considered about 30 €/m².

Also for the cladding solutions, in the InnoWEE project specific installation factors were taken into consideration, such as: scaffolding, Health & Safety costs and even design, so the range of the costs for the InnoWEE panels are foreseen to be between 54.00-97.36 €/m², without anchoring system.

The main pros of the ventilated InnoWEE solution in term of times if compared to a traditional solution are the followings:

- Precast panels;
- Easy installation method;
- The panels weigh little and are easily handled as they are small.

Prototypes panels

Prototypes panels were monitored after the installation on demo sites, in order to assess external climate conditions on products. The lessons learnt from those cracks seen in prototypes allow a better performance in real demos.

During this phase of the project, panels were monitored in relation to potential damages, failures, and colour changes during their use.

Results of the monitoring can be summarised as follows:

- **Crack and deterioration of materials**
 - ETICS-like panels: A number of cracks have slightly increased;
 - Ventilated façade panels: New cracks have arisen and previous ones expanded;
- **Colour variations**
 - ETICS-like panels: The colour of the natural panels has remained unchanged;
 - Ventilated façade panels: The colour of the panels has remained unchanged.

5.2. Modelling of energy performance of the different products

Within the Energy performance modelling, different scenarios were simulated for each demo site:

- Scenario 0: current conditions of demo buildings,
- Scenario 1: behaviour of the demos after implementation of the InnoWEE solutions,
- Scenario 2: optimization and sensitivity analysis.

Table 6. Summary information about each real demo site

Type of Pilot	Description	Location	InnoWEE solution
Pilot	Pilot site (Pilot House at CNR)	Italy (Padova)	Ventilated façade Radiant ceiling ETICS-like
Historical	Old city hall of Voula municipal	Greece (Voula)	ETICS-like Ventilated façade
New	Residential Eco-house, Putte-Mechelen	Belgium (Putte)	Radiant Ceiling
Existing	Don Orione Residential Care Center, Voluntari	Romania (Bucharest)	ETICS-like

Italian pilot site

The Pilot House is a building located inside the National Research Council Area in Padova, Italy. It was built around 1993 as a single-story office building and the structure is made of prefabricated walls. The Pilot House was used as an office until 2016 when the people using the structure were relocated in other sites of the Area. The floorplan of the building is almost a square, with an area slightly higher than 70 m² and an orientation that is close to North-South. The building comprises three main rooms, a small room, a bathroom, and a corridor for a total volume close to 200 m³.

The original floorplan of the building comprises three main rooms (zones A, B, C) and an area covering a small room, a bathroom, and a corridor (zone D). The floorplan of the building, with indication of the rooms, is shown in the Figure 83.

Figure 83. Zones of the Pilot Site where different panels were installed

Zone A – ETICS-like panels: reduction in energy demand of 10% in heating season and 15% in cooling season.

Zone B – ventilated façade: 1% reduction in winter and summer seasons, due to the good transmittance of the existing wall.

Zone C – radiant ceilings: panels installed are enough to heat all the room up to the 20°C required in Winter season and up to 26°C required in Summer season, increasing the performances respect to the fan-coil installed previously.

Figure 84. Reduction of energy consumption changing the thickness of the EPS

Greek demo historic site

The City Hall of Vouliagmeni is a historical building located in park of a residential area in the Municipality of Voula-Vouliagmeni, Greece. It was designed in the late sixties and is composed of two floors and a partial basement. All constructions details, activity levels, internal gains, weather data and HVAC design were applied to the simulation.

Figure 85. Building Model – Voula Town Hall

Figure 86. Existing Town Hall of Voula

Figure 87. Building Model Sun path – Voula Town Hall

According to IPMVP methodology, the building simulation needs to be adjusted, "calibrated", so its results match both the demand and consumption data from monthly utility bills within acceptable tolerances. It is a well-known fact that behavioural patterns have a considerable impact on the real

consumption. Therefore, there is a percentage error between measured data and simulation outputs which rely on predictive indicators. A number of procedures were applied to address that performance gap between the electricity bills provided and the building model. The calibration results are shown in graph below (Figure 88).

Figure 88. Calibration of Building Model with Measured Data

Both the ETICS-like panels and the ventilated façade are integrated in the existing building model in order to obtain the energy savings of those effects. Office 1 and Office 2 in the Ground Floor are given as the selected zones to carry out the analysis.

Figure 89. Rooms of the demo site with ETICS-like and ventilated panels on external walls.

The results from comparing the existing building condition with the renovated building, show a total annual energy performance improvement for both solutions. The annual dynamic simulation displays an energy saving of 10.41% kWh/year for Office 1 and 2.44% kWh/year for Office 2.

Figure 90. Thermal loads of Voula Town Hall before and after ETICS insulation

Furthermore, the annual energy savings with different ETICS-like insulation were calculated depending on the thickness of the insulation layer. According to the results it was claimed that:

- Electricity consumption can grow with more than 8 cm of insulation, due to an increase in cooling demand
- 8 cm of insulation will give a return in approximately thirteen years by considering the given prices. The cost-effective analysis of the solutions assumes:
 - Cost of electricity: 0.16 €/kWh,
 - Inflation on the cost of electricity: 3%.

Figure 91. Annual energy savings depending on EPS thickness in InnoWEE ETICS-like panels in the Greek demo site

Figure 92. Cost savings depending on EPS thickness in InnoWEE ETICS-like panels in the Greek demo.

Regarding the ventilated façade, there is no a sensible payback period since the first capital investment is considerable high when compared with the energy savings. As described previously, an external wall insulation is advised along with the ventilated façade in order to avoid condensations. The next line chart depicts the potential energy savings related to the thickness of that insulation of $\lambda = 0.038 \text{ W/mK}$. There is a relevant decrease of the energy consumption with the addition of 4 and 6 cm of insulation. However, it grows slightly from 6 to 10 cm.

Figure 93. Ventilated Façade including external wall insulation

Belgian demo site

In the Eco-House commercial ceiling radiant panels were compared with InnoWEE ceiling radiant panels.

Figure 94. Analysed room with the radiant panels

Considering that the construction of this demo site has been recently finalised, the results of the simulations will be verified after a testing period in the site. The thermostat of the analysed room has been set at 20°C for both the cases and from the graph below (Figure 95) it is immediately clear the improvement of the energy performance.

Figure 95. Hourly values for a heating period of the room temperature using either the commercial panels or the InnoWEE panels and the power supplied by the panels

Romanian demo site

The demo site located in Romania is a multi-purpose room within a residential care home for elderly people and orphans with physical and learning disabilities. The one floor building has a rectangular shape design and a simple ground floor structure, with a structure made out of tensed beams and concrete pillars. In the Romanian demo, the ETICS-like panels have been installed on two external walls of the storage room of the buildings.

Figure 96. Romanian demo site's plan with the storage room

Regarding the HVAC system, there is not heating or cooling system on-site and occupancy is excessively low. Therefore, there is not real consumption associated and only demand will be considered. As no meter data is available, it is not possible to calibrate the building model as previous cases. However, the comparison of the heating demand with a standard building of similar features¹ in the same scenario shows that the value is within the range of validity.

ETICS implementation result in 20% total energy savings as can be seen in table below.

Table 7. Comparison between heat demand of the storage room before (scenario 0) and after (scenario 2) installation of the InnoWEE panels

Month	Existing storage room – scenario 0	Storage room with installed panels – scenario 2
	Heating [kWh]	Heating [kWh]
January	375.09	296.80
February	222.16	173.97
March	63.08	41.61
April	1.52	1.01
May	0	0
June	0	0

¹ <http://webtool.building-typology.eu/#bm>

July	0	0
August	0	0
September	0	0
October	12.22	7.67
November	118.16	86.28
December	302.69	238.25
TOTAL [kWh/yr]	1,094.92	845.59
TOTAL [kWh/m²yr]	49.77	38.43

In order to fully study the potential of the improved design, the installation of the ETICS-like panels with different insulation thickness has been assessed. The design needs to be optimized with realistic and cost-effective parameters, reaching a compromise between costs and energy performance. The design is based on:

- Reducing the energy demand
- Optimising the insulation thickness
- Economic aspects, investment costs.

Thickness (cm)	Energy demand (kWh/year)	Savings
0	1094.92	0.00%
2	1011.88	7.58%
3	971	11.32%
5	915.47	16.39%
6	895.24	18.24%
7	877.89	19.82%
8	863.87	21.10%
9	851.31	22.25%

Figure 97. Total annual energy saving for different insulation thickness

First graph above depicts the annual energy savings with different thickness of insulation material. It is apparent that the demand reduces with the thickness increase. That reduction goes from 7.58% for 2 cm until 22.25% for 9 cm. However, it is remarkable from both the figure and the table that the estimated energy saving percentage becomes less and less noticeable above 6 cm of insulation. In fact, those savings grow slightly by 2.43% between 7 cm and 9 cm addition.

Figure 98. Accumulative cashflow for Romania Demo Site

With regards to the accumulative cashflow, it can be concluded that the ETICS installation is recovered in 16 years when 2 cm of insulation are installed. Nevertheless, there is not return expected above 7 cm.

These analyses are based on the following assumptions:

- Cost of electricity: 0.099 €/kWh,
- Inflation on the cost of electricity: 3%.

5.3. Hygrothermal assessment

Simplified one-dimensional heat flow calculations do not consider the impact of thermal bridges such as the support brackets of the InnoWEE system. For a more precise assessment of thermal performance and risk of surface condensation or mould growth, three-dimensional numerical modelling has been performed. A range of different thicknesses of thermal insulation has been assessed, with this insulation placed against the external surface of the original wall facing the ventilated cavity.

The temperature factor (defined in ISO 13788) has been used as a metric for evaluating the risk of surface condensation or mould growth. The internal surface temperature sits within a scale from 0 (external air temperature) to 1 (internal air temperature) in a steady-state condition, with lower values indicating a higher risk of condensation. Risk thresholds depend on external climate and indoor ambient conditions. As a conservative approach, the most vulnerable demonstration building has been selected, which is the demo of Voula, with 0.62 as the worst-case threshold. All cases incorporating insulation have a temperature factor above 0.80 and are therefore considered safe.

Figure 99. Hygrothermal assessment EN ISO 13788:2012

Regarding thermal performance, with no air gaps around the support bracket, the thermal bridge causes an increase of 8-14% in the U-value, which is considered reasonable. However, with air gaps around anchors, the U-value increases 25-70%, causing a significant reduction of overall thermal performance. Therefore, it is recommended to use flexible insulants and wrap them with care around support brackets to prevent such air gaps.

Figure 100. Ventilated façade: no insulation (left), 60 mm insulation with no gap around anchor (center), 60 mm insulation with an air gap in the projection of the anchor (right)

5.4. InnoWEE achievements and project design for each demo site

In the tables below InnoWEE achievement regarding energy savings and CO₂ emission savings are presented.

Table 8. InnoWEE energy achievements

Scenario	Baseline (final energy)		INNOWEE renovations			
	Heating demand [kWh/m ² ·yr]	Cooling demand [kWh/m ² ·yr]	Heating demand [kWh/m ² ·yr]	Reduction [%]	Cooling demand [kWh/m ² ·yr]	Reduction [%]
Italy (ETICS, zone A)	45.77	0.8	40.95	11.8	0.69	18.8
Italy (VF, zone B)	41.62	1.03	41.08	1.13	1.02	0.97
Greece (ETICS)	52.75	40.39	35.83	32	40.85	-1.1
Greece (VF)	42.99	40.73	39.32	8.5	41.18	-1.1
Romania	49.77	0	39.90	20	0	-

Table 9. InnoWEE CO₂ achievements

Scenario	Baseline (final energy)		INNOWEE renovations			
	Heating demand [g/kWh·yr]	Cooling demand [g/kWh·yr]	Heating demand [g/kWh·yr]	Reduction [%]	Cooling demand [g/kWh·yr]	Reduction [%]
Italy (ETICS)	339.45	6.08	303.73	10.5	5.14	15
Greece (ETICS)	1088.27	920.77	739.76	32	928.73	0.86
Greece (VF)	626.61	657.92	573.20	8.5	664.07	-0.93
Romania	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

For the purpose of defining the specific rehabilitation project for each demo site, a validation of the new products in real scale is needed. For this, an analysis of the characteristics of each demo sites was carried out to understand the specific details for the elaboration of the installation projects of the panels. It was performed based on information gathered previously, especially:

- geographical localization,
- seismic risk,
- exposure,
- use,
- installations facilities.

6. Life Cycle Assessment

Researchers, policy-makers and companies are more and more focused on lowering the ecological impact of buildings and materials implemented in them. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a standardized technique that addresses the environmental impacts associated with different stages of a product's life cycle. These stages include raw material extraction, delivery of extracted resources to factory, material processing and manufacturing of the product, transport to the construction site and installation phase, product use, repair and maintenance, and finally product re-use, recycling or final disposal, including benefits of the product beyond its life-cycle, in the next product system (ISO14040:2006, ISO14044:2006, EN 15804). In the field of CDW management, LCA has been applied to investigate the performance of general CDW management strategies and CDW recycling plants, compare natural material to recycled material from CDW, analyse different end-of-life scenarios for buildings and construction elements and evaluate electricity production from CDW (Bovea and Powell, 2016).

LCA consists of four distinct phases:

- **the goal and scope definition phase**, which sets out the context of the study by defining functional unit, system boundaries and any assumptions and limitations of the study
- **the inventory analysis phase**, which creates an inventory of input and output flows to and from the studied system, such as inputs of water, energy, and raw materials, and outputs (emissions) to air, land and water
- **the impact assessment phase**, which aims at evaluating the significance and magnitude of potential environmental impacts based on the inventory analysis flow results
- **the interpretation phase**, where the findings from the results of the inventory analysis phase and/or the impact assessment phase are summarised and evaluated in relation to the defined goal and scope of the study.

Life cycle assessment as a method has some limitations, but it can be used as an effective tool to define some common trends. LCA in our study (the case of **recycled CDW based materials**) focuses on:

- Detailed upstream modelling,
- Good definition of scenarios,
- Dealing with methodology for different end-of-life scenarios,
- Defining appropriate system boundaries.

6.1. LCA methodology

The goal of the LCA analysis within the InnoWEE project is to investigate the environmental impacts associated with different life cycle stages of the prefabricated geopolymeric panels made from large fractions of recycled construction and demolition waste (CDW). Three different prefabricated geopolymeric panels have been considered: (i) ETICS-like panel, (ii) cladding panel for ventilated façades, and (iii) radiant panel.

The analysis is based on the declared unit of the considered product. The declared unit used is 1 m² of the considered prefabricated geopolymeric panel, i.e. ETICS-like façade panel, cladding panel for ventilated façades and radiant panel.

This LCA study is based on the **cradle to grave** principle and considers the entire life cycle of the prefabricated geopolymeric panels, i.e. product stage (A1-A3), construction process stage (A4-A5),

use stage (B1-B7), end-of-life stage (C1-C4), and benefits and loads beyond the system boundary (D). Modules (A1-D) are as defined in EN 15804.

The **product stage** consists of (i) production of materials, including extraction of raw materials, (ii) transport of materials to the panel production plant, (iii) production of the prefabricated geopolymeric panels, which includes mixing of the constituent materials, casting, curing, demoulding, drying, assembling and finally packaging and storing of the produced prefabricated geopolymeric panels. The energy (e.g. mixing, casting, curing, transport inside the plant etc.) and water (e.g. water for cleaning etc.) consumption in the overall production process is also taken into consideration.

The **construction process stage** consists of transport of the panels to the construction site (i.e. module A4) and installation of the panels (i.e. module A5). A transport distance of 200 km has been selected and all supporting materials used within the installation process (e.g. fasteners, mortar, body anchors etc.) have been included in the LCA model.

Once the panels are installed, the **use stage** of the prefabricated geopolymeric panels begins. In the 30 year life expectancy of the panels, some maintenance work (B2) and repair (B3) is required. A scenario of cleaning the panels with water and a rinsing agent every five years has been used for the B2 module and minor repairs with a sealing compound every ten years for B3 module. Other mediation is not required.

The applied **end-of-life stage** concept assumes that the geopolymer part of the panel could be recycled and used as a replacement of virgin aggregate in roadbed, while non-recyclable parts of the panel (e.g. EPS etc.) would be disposed at landfill. There are no impacts associated with the demolition of the panels (i.e. module C1), since the demolition is done manually. The non-recyclable parts (e.g. EPS etc.) have been transported to landfill (i.e. module C4), with the transport distance being set to 50 km. The geopolymer recycling rate has been set to 70%, which means that 70% of the geopolymer obtained after the demolition process has been transported to the recycling plant (i.e. module C3), while 30% has been transported to the landfill (i.e. module C4). The transport distance to the recycling plant (i.e. module C2) has been also set to 50 km. In the recycling plant, the geopolymer is crushed to the required particle size (i.e. module C3).

When the end-of-waste state is reached, it is assumed that the crushed HDG is going to be used in road base, which would avoid the use of virgin material for road construction. Therefore, the **benefits and loads beyond the system boundary stage** (i.e. module D), includes the impacts of the transport to the road construction site and the benefits (negative sign) due to the replacement of virgin material in the road construction. The transport distance to the road construction site has been set to 50 km. The secondary material (i.e. recycled geopolymer) does not have the same quality as the virgin material. Therefore, a value-correction factor has been applied in order to take into account the difference in the material quality. A value of 0.5 has been applied for the value-correction factor, which means that calculated benefits due to the replacement of virgin material are multiplied with the value-correction factor of 0.5.

6.2. Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)

GaBi modelling software has been used to conduct the LCA study (thinkstep, 2019b), with GaBi being one of the most commonly used software programs in the field of LCA modelling (Herrmann and Moltesen, 2015). The LCA modelling approach is a combination of data provided in the database inventory and individual upstream modelling. Raw material extraction and processing, processing

of secondary material, delivery of materials and the production and supply of energy and water have been modelled based on the inventory data given in the GaBi Professional database. However, three input materials are not readily available in the GaBi Professional database: metakaolin, potassium silicate and CDW, reflecting actual composition of the CDW used. Therefore, these have been modelled separately in the upstream LCA modelling process.

LCA upstream modelling:

- Metakaolin: production is based on crushing of kaolin in grinder, subsequent drying of the crushed kaolin and calcination of crushed kaolin to metakaolin in a blast furnace.
 - Main inputs to upstream LCA model: kaolin and energy requirements.
- Potassium silicate: a hydrothermal production of potassium silicate solutions is based on the reaction of a silicon dioxide source with aqueous potassium hydroxide.
 - Main inputs to upstream LCA model: potassium hydroxide, silicon dioxide source (e.g. silica sand), energy and water requirements.
- Construction and demolition waste (CDW): Different methods for the calculation of environmental burdens of waste have been applied in the LCA study of CDW. In the final calculation, the cut-off method has been used to model the recycled content, which means that the secondary or recycled materials bear only the impacts of the recycling processes.
 - Main inputs to upstream LCA model: energy and water requirements.

6.3. Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

The environmental impact assessment has been calculated at the midpoint level with the CML 2001 impact assessment method. The CML 2001 impact assessment method restricts quantitative modelling to early stages in the cause-effect chain to limit uncertainties, with results being grouped in midpoint categories according to common mechanisms (e.g. climate change) or commonly accepted groupings (e.g. ecotoxicity) (Guinée, 2002). The main principles behind the CML 2001 methodology are based on ISO 14040 and 14044 standards, and the characterisation factors are updated when new knowledge on substance level is available (e.g. the last update dates to January 2016) (thinkstep, 2019b). The results of the CML 2001 impact assessment method can be presented in terms of different impact potentials. The CML 2001 impact assessment method however does not evaluate the primary energy demand (i.e. primary energy from renewable and non-renewable resources) and the total use of fresh water (i.e. fresh water consumption). Therefore, primary energy demand and total use of fresh water have been evaluated separately within the GaBi modelling software. Different impact potential and energy demand calculated in the LCA are presented in Table 10.

Table 10. LCA impact categories and units used for their characterisation

Impact category	Abbreviation	Unit
Global warming potential	GWP	[kg CO ₂ eq.]
Global warming potential excluding biogenic carbon	GWP excl. biog. carbon	[kg CO ₂ eq.]
Acidification potential	AP	[kg SO ₂ eq.]
Eutrophication potential	EP	[kg PO ₄ -3 eq.]
Human toxicity potential	HTP	[kg DCB eq.]
Ozone layer depletion potential	ODP	[kg R11 eq.]
Photochemical ozone potential creation	POCP	[kg Ethene eq.]
Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity potential	FAETP	[kg DCB eq.]

Marine aquatic ecotoxicity potential	MAETP	[kg DCB eq.]
Terrestrial ecotoxicity potential	TETP	[kg DCB eq.]
Abiotic depletion (elements)	ADP el.	[kg Sb eq.]
Abiotic depletion (fossil)	ADP fos.	[MJ]
Primary energy from non-renewable resources	PENRT	[MJ]
Primary energy from renewable resources	PERT	[MJ]
Fresh water consumption	WATER	[kg]

6.4. LCA interpretation

Figure 101 shows the environmental impacts associated with different life cycle stages of the prefabricated geopolymeric ETICS-like panel. It can be seen from Figure 101 that the product stage (i.e. modules A1-A3) contributes the most to the environmental footprint of the considered prefabricated geopolymeric panel. The other life cycle stage that has a more significant environmental impact is the construction process stage (i.e. module A5) in terms of ADP el. and HTP. All other life cycle stages have minimal impact on the environmental performance of the prefabricated geopolymeric panels.

Figure 101. Results of LCA for ETICS-like panels

Similarly, Figure 102 shows the environmental impacts associated with different life cycle stages of the prefabricated geopolymeric cladding panel for ventilated facades. The product stage (i.e. modules A1-A3) again contributes the most to the environmental footprint of the considered prefabricated geopolymeric panel. The other life cycle stage that has a more significant environmental impact is the construction process stage (i.e. module A5) in terms of ADP el., HTP, POCP and TETP. All other life cycle stages have minimal impact on the environmental performance of the cladding panel.

Figure 102. Results of LCA for cladding panels for ventilated façades

Finally, Figure 103 shows the environmental impacts associated with different life cycle stages of the prefabricated geopolymeric radiant panels. The product stage (i.e. modules A1-A3) again contributes the most to the environmental footprint of the considered prefabricated geopolymeric panel. The other life cycle stage that has a more significant environmental impact is the construction process stage (i.e. module A5) in terms of ADP el. and HTP. As in other types of panels, all other life cycle stages have minimal impact on the environmental performance of the radiant panel.

Figure 103. Results of LCA for radiant panels

The presented LCA modelling results have shown that the product stage (i.e. modules A1-A3) contributes the most to the environmental footprint of the considered prefabricated geopolymeric panels. Therefore, any potential reduction of the environmental burden associated with the life

cycle of the considered prefabricated geopolymeric panels should be based primarily on the potential improvements of the panel production process.

7. Life Cycle Cost – LCC

Life Cycle Cost (LCC) is calculated if there is a need to know the true cost of a product over time (not only the initial cost) since very often, costs arising over the life time of a product exceed initial production costs. In the LCC calculation different costs are detected, as can be seen from Figure 101. The approach to the calculation of LCC for InnoWEE panels selected is a modular approach i.e. breaking down the costs in individual life-cycle stages, that are the same as in the LCA.

Figure 104 shows the schematic drawing, presenting relation of whole life cycle costs (WLC) of a building and life cycle costs (LCC), applied on a product. Coloured squares have been addressed in the LCC analysis of the prefabricated geopolymers panels. Operation and occupancy costs do not relate directly to the InnoWEE product and therefore the contribution is set to zero.

Figure 104. Schematics of InnoWEE LCC analysis

In the Figure 104, it is also indicated how the modularity of the life cycle is taken into account. There are separate input costs calculations for production (A1-A3), installation (A5) use phase (B1-B7), and end-of life phase (C) calculated. B6-B7 are set to zero, because the product does not consume energy or other valuable substances (e.g. water). Transport (A4) is omitted because it is specific for each building.

In external costs, possible costs of emissions are assessed as for example CO₂ emissions would contribute to the price of the system, although they are allocated in A3 module. The cost is directly related to CO₂ emissions as measured by GWP in LCA.

For the calculation of the LCC for InnoWEE products, specific assumptions have been taken into account:

- production cost of the prototypes is known and serves as a basis,
- industrialization is realistically taken into account,
- installation costs are based on project data and comparable data,
- maintenance of the installed products is subject to scenarios and depend on location and specific use conditions,
- costs related to End-of-life (module C): demolition cost, transport costs, fees and taxes (e.g. cost for disposal to landfill) are based on current prices;
 - this cost highly depends on location of the landfill,
 - generally the cost of disposal rises,
- environmental costs, related to production (emissions of CO₂, NO/NO_x and SO₂) are considered, but only CO₂ emission costs are detected.

All the assumptions are based on carefully assessed parameters, providing a realistic final cost calculation result.

The ambiguities that affect final LCC results are mainly connected with the location of the building, where InnoWEE products are to be installed. Major factors, that are location driven, are (i) cost of workforce, (ii) local availability of specific components and (iii) climatic conditions that may affect (i.e. decrease, compared to current calculation) maintenance costs.

In this calculation, costs are originating either from the project data itself or (such as landfill costs) form official sources.

Figure 105. Life cycle cost (LCC) – Results in scenario of industrialization

The calculation in Figure 105 shows the evolution of the cost over time. It is clear that the initial product cost (at time 0) is relatively low. The installation cost (in the first year, indicated with LCC rise in year 0) depends on specific location. If the installation cost is smaller (e.g. cheaper workforce or larger area covered) the entire curve is shifted downwards. The costs, arising in the use phase (B1-B5) calculated are on the safe side. Further maintenance optimization (e.g. general building maintenance interventions instead of particular interventions) may reduce the cost of maintenance. Overall, the LCC data shows good results for the assessed products.

Figure 106. Methodology for preliminary cost assessment of produced SRM

Assessment of the behaviour of the product over its entire life cycle consists of assessing its environmental performance, using the LCA method and its economic performance, using the LCCA method. The LCA has revealed strengths and hotspots of the InnoWEE HDG based products. However, because of the product being currently in the development stage that does not include full industrialization, further reduction of the environmental burdens is expected. Along with the industrialization, further optimization in terms of energy supply for the assessed products is possible. Since the production phase contributes most in almost all considered indicators, most of the optimization can be done in this life cycle phase, especially on energy supply by the introduction of renewable energy (e.g. solar energy).

Life cycle cost approach gives additional insight in the cost evolvement over time and shows that the production cost is not the explicitly dominant. It is shown that maintenance cost also strongly depends on the location of the building, due to workforce cost as well as the environmental burdening of the exposed elements. It should be noted that estimates are on the safe side regarding the frequency of interventions.

In general, taking into account both environmental and cost analysis, InnoWEE products are comparable to similar products on the market. On top of that, after the industrialization of production, InnoWEE boards have great potential to surpass comparable products in the market.

8. Conclusions

In the framework of European Union policies towards sustainability and circular economy, the H2020 European RIA project InnoWEE – “*Innovative pre-fabricated components including different waste construction materials reducing building energy and minimising environmental impacts*” – started in 2016, developed three types of architectural prefabricated panels for improving the energy performance of buildings, which account for about 40% of the total energy consumption in the EU. InnoWEE target applications included existing buildings needing renovation, with special attention to those belonging to the Cultural Heritage. These panels were manufactured with innovative geopolymer binders developed on purpose, able to embed large quantities of construction and demolition waste aggregates, in compliance with the EU goals set by the Waste Framework Directive.

Indeed, InnoWEE went in 4 years through a path intentionally similar to that of a company willing to develop a product from the concept to the potential market introduction. The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of each type of panel was successfully raised from 3 (proof of concept) to 6/7 (demonstration in relevant/operational environment), tackling their development with a holistic approach that faced all the following aspects: technological issues, technical standards and regulations in force, health and safety concerns, market placement, industrial and business planning, and finally life cycle analysis.

Thus, in a context of sustainability and circular economy, geopolymer materials and industrial-like manufacturing methods of the panels were investigated and optimized to achieve performant and cost effective products. The fitness for the intended use and the thermal effectiveness of panels were tested in laboratory and in demo building installations, then the latter was validated through calibrated numerical models. The industrial and business planning virtually exploited the market potential of these products, and the environmental, social and economic impacts have been appraised as well.

More in detail, geopolymer materials, which constituted the main component of InnoWEE panels and embedded up to 50% of recycled aggregates from CDW, were extensively investigated and, finally, the heuristic optimization that was carried out managed to suit the requirements of an industrial-like production and to ensure a satisfactory quality of the final products. Moreover, their suitability to be reused at the end-of-life as recycled aggregates was preliminarily assessed, thus suggesting a potential feasibility of a closed loop production.

Three types of panels, i.e. for external ETICS-like insulation, for ventilated façades and for interior radiant hydronic heating/cooling, were designed, prototyped and manufactured with a Technology Upscaling Pilot Plant, which was successfully conceived and implemented on purpose.

The panels have been extensively tested with regard to their mechanical and physical characteristics and durability performance, following the provisions of selected ETAGs and ENs. The following parameters were assessed: capillary water uptake, water vapour permeability, impact resistance, bond strength, freeze thaw behaviour, freezing in the presence of de-icing salt, resistance to carbonation, alkali silica reactivity, and sulphate resistance. Except for the resistance to freezing in the presence of de-icing salt, all other results were comparable to, or performances even exceeded cement based products.

The installation on four demo buildings located in different climate regions (Greece, Belgium, Italy and Romania), which were monitored before and after, allowed a systematic study of the thermal

performance in operation, thus providing valuable data for numerical modelling. Durability of external applications was under observation as well, thanks to Non-Destructive Testing periodically carried out.

The real demo buildings provided a collection of data used in Building Energy Modelling (BEM) to validate simulation strategies and to calibrate models. Based on data retrieved from monitoring systems, 3D simulations of four virtual demo buildings (located in Italy, Greece, Romania and Spain) allowed appraising the performance of panels in different situations and achieving an optimal design based on different scenarios.

Finally, LCA analyses, calculated for the pilot plant shows favourable results with respect to the environmental impacts. The exposed hot-spots reveal points of further optimisation and full upscaling that ultimately leads to overall better environmental performance compared to the solutions commercially available on the market. The cost analysis also shows potential for competitive products once the products are fully up-scaled and the production fully industrialized.

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List of abbreviations and symbols

Abbreviations

6σ	Six Sigma methodology	GWP	Global Warming Potential
AAM	Alkali Activate Materials	H2020	Horizon 2020 Framework Programme
AC	Alternating Current	HDG	High-Density Geopolymer
ADP	Abiotic DePletion	hEN	harmonized European Standard/Norm
AP	Acidification Potential	HTP	Human Toxicity Potential
ASR	Alkali Silica Reactivity	ICP MS	Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials	InnoWEE	Innovative pre-fabricated components including different Waste construction materials reducing building Energy and minimising Environmental impacts
AVCP	Assessment and Verification of Constancy of Performance	ISO	International Organization for Standardization
BIM	Building Information Modelling	K-sil	Potassium silicate
BEM	Building Energy Modelling	LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
C&D	Construction and Demolition	LCC	Life Cycle Cost
CDW	Construction and Demolition Waste	LCCA	Life Cycle Cost Analysis
CE	Conformité Européenne	LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging	LEEMA	Low Embodied Energy Insulation MAterials and Masonry Components for Energy Efficient Buildings
CO₂	Carbon DiOxide	MAETP	Marine Aquatic EcoToxicity Potential
CPR	Construction Products Regulation	MK	MetaKaolin
DMAIC	Define, Measure, Analyse, Improve, Control	NDT	Non-Destructive Testing
EAD	European Assessment Document	NO/NO_x	Nitrogen Oxide/s
EC	European Commission	NPT	Net Production Time
EFT	Eigen Frequency Test	ODP	Ozone layer Depletion Potential
EN	European Norm (standard)	PAH	Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon
EOTA	European Organisation for Technical Assessment	PCB	PolyChlorinated Biphenyl
EoW	End of Waste	PENRT	Primary Energy from Non-Renewable resources
EP	Eutrophication Potential	PERT	Primary Energy from Renewable resources
EPS	Expanded PolyStyrene	PEST	Political, Economic, Social and Technological
ETA	European Technical Assessment	PEX-a	Cross-linked polyethylene
ETAG	European Technical Approval Guideline	PMV	Predicted Mean Vote
ETICS	External Thermal Insulation Composite System	POCP	Photochemical Ozone Potential Creation
EU	European Union	PP	PolyPropylene
FA	Fly Ash		
FAETP	Freshwater Aquatic EcoToxicity Potential		
FE	Finite Element		
FEM	Finite Element Modelling		

PPD	Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied	TRL	Technology Readiness Level
PU	PolyUrethane	TUPP	Technology Upscaling Pilot Plant
QAP	Quality Assurance Plan	UHTS	Ultra-High Tensile Strength
R&I	Research & Innovation	UPS	Uninterruptible Power Supply
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals	UPV	Ultrasonic Pulse transit time
RH	Relative Humidity	VF	Ventilated Façade
RIA	Research Innovation Action	VOC	Volatile Organic Compounds
SHT	Surface Heat Tread	WG	Wood Geopolymer
SO₂	Sulphur DiOxide	WGP	Wood Geopolymer Panel
SRM	Secondary Raw Material	WLC	Whole Life Cycle
SWA	Surface Water Absorption	WP	Work Package
TAB	Technical Assessment Body	XPS	EXtruded PolyStyrene
TETP	Terrestrial EcoToxicity Potential	XRF	X-Ray Fluorescence
TOC	Total Organic Carbon		

Symbols

P	Power	m²	square meter
T	Temperature	m³	cubic meter
%	Percent	kg/m²	kilogram per square meter
°C	Celsius degree	N/mm²	Newton per square meter
g	gram	W/m⁻¹·K⁻¹	Watt per meter per Kelvin
kg	kilogram	min	minute
km	kilometre	kWh	kiloWatt-hour
m	meter	€	Euro
cm	centimetre	kWh/yr	kiloWatt-hour per year
mm	millimetre	kWh/m²·yr	kiloWatt-hour per square meter per year
µm	micrometre		

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